

ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION AND SUSTAINABILITY

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Declaration of Honour

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A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'E. J. ...', written in a cursive style.

Signature

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Abstract

Purpose and Background: This study explores the determinants of entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainability and investigates if sustainable business practices impact financial performance and the direction of association. Entrepreneurship and sustainability exhibit a complex interaction, with studies suggesting that the relationship makes economic growth more efficient. However, many studies present different results on the impact of Environmental, Social and Governance on financial performance. Whether Kingdom of Saudi Arabia government and entrepreneurs' intentions are geared towards sustainability remains a widely contested question. As a result, this study was conducted to determine the determinants of entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainability among KSA companies and whether sustainable business practices impacted financial performance. ESG scores and ESG risk ratings were utilized as proxy measures of sustainability, whereas Return on Assets and Return on Equity were used as measures of financial performance. The company management rating provided by Sustainalytics was used as a proxy for measuring determinants of entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainability.

Method: The study adopted a mixed research method encompassing a quantitative study of 17 corporations in KSA from different sectors and a systematic review of 41 sources following PRISMA 2020 expanded checklist and PROSPERO's guidelines. The quantitative research covered descriptive statistics and inferential statistical analysis, allowing for the determination of causation. Findings from the systematic literature review were used to triangulate quantitative analysis findings, thereby improving the study's validity. Regarding inferential statistical analysis, multinomial regression analysis was run to determine the association between management and sustainability efforts. After that, three linear regression models were run, one investigating the association between debt-to-assets ratio and financial performance among the studied KSA companies and the

other two investigating the association between sustainable business practices and financial performance.

Results: Descriptive statistical analysis revealed a weak management rating exhibited by 47.1% of the studied companies, suggesting potential vulnerabilities in internal controls, strategic planning, and stakeholder engagement, which are all important to sustainability. Besides, reading exposure to ESG risk, KSA companies generally exhibit medium exposure to ESG risks, accounting for 58.8% of the companies across different sectors of the economy. The medium exposure to ESG risk is seconded, with high exposure accounting for 29.4%, whereas companies least exposed to ESG risk account for 11.8%. Regarding ESG risk rating, only 5.9% of the studied companies recorded low ESG rating risk. Inferential statistical analysis showed that the debt-to-assets ratio did not impact the performance of the studied KSA companies. Besides, sustainable business practices did not affect the financial performance of the companies studied. However, a significant association between management and sustainable business practices was evident, returning a p-value less than 0.05.

Conclusion: Managerial factors were ascertained as a significant determinant of entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainability from a broader context with specific context encompassing factors such as perception of ESG-related risks, management stakeholders' personal beliefs and values, organizational culture, knowledge, brand image, supporting technologies, consumers awareness, culture, and government policy. While management determined entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainability, sustainable business practices had an insignificant influence on financial performance, explaining less than 3% of the variability in financial performance.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Intention, Sustainable Entrepreneurship, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Social and Financial Performance, Corporate Social Responsibility, Environmental, Social, and Governance investing.

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List of Abbreviations

SEIs: Social Entrepreneurial Initiatives

SMEs: Small and Medium-sized Enterprises

TBL: Triple Bottom Line

ESG: Environmental, Social, and Governance

NGOs: Non-Governmental Organizations

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

DUAs: Data Use Agreements

KSA: Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

CSR: Corporate Social Responsibility

1. Introduction

This chapter of this thesis provides a general overview of background information on the study topic, highlights the relevance of the chosen topic, articulates the problem under study, states the relevance and benefits of the study, highlights goals to be attained on completing the study, provides insight into the anticipated study methodology, and presented the overview scope and structure of the study.

Investors and policymakers place significant importance on sustainability and entrepreneurship. KSA serves as an example of how business and sustainability are intricately intertwined, showing the complexity faced by nations worldwide. The economy of the KSA is reliant on its oil reserves. As it enacts reforms to lessen its reliance on oil, diversify its sources of revenue, and increase its competitiveness, its economy is changing. The government created the 2020 National Transformation Program (NTP) and Vision 2030 in an attempt to steer the nation toward sustainable economic growth and prosperity. When combined, these strategic plans provide ambitious targets and goals aimed at making the nation sustainable, diversified, and a hub for international trade. The KSA government prioritizes diversification and enhancements to the commercial and regulatory environments to establish a sustainable business climate. Consequently, the government of the KSA has enacted new legislation to encourage entrepreneurship, safeguard investors' interests, and cut down on business expenses, new investment agreements, and permits. Furthermore, funding has been deployed by the Saudi Investment Fund (PIF), among other purposes, such as encouraging private sector investment.

The KSA government has placed entrepreneurship at the top of the national agenda. The Saudi government encourages young people to pursue entrepreneurship as a career and promotes their involvement in entrepreneurial endeavours. The government views small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) as a significant economic force, and by 2030, they hope to grow their share of the GDP from 20% to 35%. To assist the SME sectors, the

government created a specific authority known as "Monsha'at" and encouraged innovation and entrepreneurship. Towards this end, Long-term agreements for trade and information sharing with other nations worldwide would be sought to achieve this goal. The national strategic vision is likewise dedicated to strengthening the labour force by making large expenditures on the education and training of the upcoming generations—both male and female. Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), which boost exports, generate employment, and encourage innovation, are also acknowledged throughout the nation as significant drivers of economic development.

Sustainable development is largely dependent on entrepreneurship, which is a substantial economic activity in many nations. One of the most important policy priorities to progressively generate jobs and decrease poverty is to encourage entrepreneurship. Thus, in an effort to further socioeconomic growth, they are gradually encouraging entrepreneurial endeavors. States aim to encourage an entrepreneurial attitude by increasing funding for initiatives that support it. This is part of their efforts to make their societies more entrepreneur-friendly. Economic diversification is now required in Saudi Arabia as it is doubtful that oil prices would rise significantly in the future. Increasing diversity would assist in creating the non-oil economy, boost productivity and sustainable growth, lessen reliance on the volatility and unpredictability of the world oil market, and help create jobs in the private sector.

The particular social setting of KSA makes the discussion of sustainability and entrepreneurship more nuanced. A delicate balance between tradition and innovation fosters the growth of entrepreneurial, financially viable, and culturally significant endeavors. In order to promote entrepreneurial activity in the Kingdom's attempts to maintain its cultural past while embracing modernization, it is important to take into account how this balancing act may be both ambitious and culturally mindful. Thus, the objective of this research is to identify the driving forces behind the Kingdom of Saudi Arabian firms' adoption of sustainable business practices in this particular setting. The objective of this research is to identify the driving forces behind the Kingdom of Saudi Arabian firms' adoption of sustainable business practices in this particular setting. Consequently, the research offers scholars valuable ideas that politicians, business

development organizations, and entrepreneurs may use in the real world. It is important to comprehend the elements that contribute to the definition of entrepreneurial aspirations as Saudi Arabia moves toward a sustainable and varied future. It also helps to shed light on the controversy surrounding whether the country's sustainability initiatives are PR stunts. In this social and economic context, this knowledge is relevant to corporate alignments of sustainability norms.

1.1. Background

This subsection provides insights into the background information on the study topic. The concept of ESG is discussed, and concerns are presented on entrepreneurs' intentions in relation to adopting sustainability in KSA.

Sustainable finance forms have proliferated globally in recent years. ESG investing is no different. Portfolios managed globally following ESG investing reached 17.5 trillion US dollars in 2020, reflecting the view that ESG factors impact long-term portfolio performance and investment decisions (Boffo & Patalano, 2020). Besides, ESG investing in KSA is increasingly important, driven by regulatory support, national development, investor expectations, increased corporate responsibility, market demand, and international collaboration. Despite its wide acceptance as a mainstream form of sustainable finance, ESG practices and terminology around its use vary considerably, raising questions about entrepreneurial intentions associated with sustainability (Boffo & Patalano, 2020). It is worth noting that ESG investing stems from social responsibility investing and is currently considered a distinct form of investing, raising concerns about the association between entrepreneurial intentions and sustainability. Studies conducted in KSA showed that ESG investing lacks a noteworthy connotation with ROE and significantly reduced TOBINSQ, raising concerns about entrepreneurial intentions' association with sustainability (Firmansyah et al., 2023).

The following paragraphs elucidate the current approach KSA takes towards sustainability and the perceived intentions associated with such efforts.

Entrepreneurship and sustainability exhibit a complex interaction, with studies suggesting that the relationship makes economic growth more efficient. Entrepreneurs aligning their intentions towards sustainability result in responsible business behaviour aimed at preserving existing resources for the better of the forthcoming generation. As many nations globally struggle with a multifaceted nature of entrepreneurship sustainability, KSA presents an exciting case worth exploring, considering that despite being a high-carbon nation, it has diversified its economy away from oil and put measures to ensure businesses thriving in the kingdom remain sustainable. Besides, KSA has managed to transition from tradition to modernity while preserving its rich cultural heritage and ensuring its sustainability. Widely recognised, KSA's economy is based on hydrocarbons, given the nation's massive oil reserves. As a result, concerns arise in the global market on whether KSA's entrepreneurial intentions, including diversifying its economy, are genuinely committed to the sustainability of just a PR to attract environmentally conscious investors, making it necessary to research the topic.

KSA's Vision 2030 focuses on entrepreneurship and factors to convert KSA into a global trading hub. With more partnerships with the international community, the nation focuses on enhancing sustainability to make its market more interactive, given the surge in ESG investing. This changing terrain in KSA motivates the need to research entrepreneurial intentions in relation to sustainability and whether it works for the nation. The intersection between sustainability and financial performance indicators is often questioned in extant literature, leaving a gap for further research. Like ESG, KSA's sustainability incorporates economic and social dimensions beyond mere environmental considerations. As KSA strives to meet its Vision 2030 prospects, the nation continues to equate sustainability with resilience, adaptability, and inclusiveness in many sectors of its economy, thereby fueling "Saudization" and demanding more corporations set their headquarters in KSA. For instance, KSA currently requires all consultancy firms to have headquarters in KSA to get government contracts and employ many Saudi nationals. As the global

domineering, KSA's drive to build a sustainable economy is focused on domestic contexts –cultural and economic.

KSA's socio-cultural fabric makes the association between entrepreneurship intentions and sustainability more complex, making conducting studies on the topic necessary. Studies investigating the impact of CSR return different findings on its impact on financial performance. In fact, Sameer (2021) regards CSR as one of the most debatable research areas dating back to the 1950s, and the controversy continues to grow. Coelho et al. (2023) ascertained a significant association between CSR and financial performance, whereas Mentor (2016) determined a negative association between CSR and financial performance. Unlike these findings, Sameer (2021) determined no association between CSR and financial performance. Based on the insight, entrepreneurial intentions surging CSR remain unclear, with mixed findings associated with different ESG factors. In KSA, entrepreneurial, economically viable, and culturally resonant ventures coexist in the delicate balance of tradition and innovation. To preserve culture, KSA demands that consultancy firms all be Saudi companies to safeguard that solicitation given aligns with the national culture. Based on the insight, the kingdom requires entrepreneurial initiatives to sustain its cultural heritage. However, entrepreneurial intentions advancing sustainability remain unclear, especially from a financial performance viewpoint.

Possible factors increasing ESG investing in KSA are presented in existing literature but not extensively investigated. The following paragraphs shed length into reasons behind KSA, giving considerable attention to ESG investing and criteria, and so does sustainability from an entrepreneurial perspective.

First, current studies and industry testimonials provide insights into ESG investing in certain scenarios, improving risk management and resulting in better returns compared to conventional investing (Boffo & Patalano, 2020). Despite the presented reason increasing entrepreneurial intentions toward sustainability, growing concerns arise from the complexity of quantifying ESG-based performance. Second, society is increasingly concerned about climate change; hence, with globally accepted standards that fuel responsible business conduct, ESG will likely influence investment choices, making

entrepreneurs intend to invest in sustainability (Boffo & Patalano, 2020). Finally, there exists a surge in investors and financial institutions moving towards sustainable long-term returns from short-term risk, making it necessary for them to align investment decisions with accepted societal standards and values (Boffo & Patalano, 2020). Central banks in many nations globally are currently considering transitioning their financial systems to low-carbon economies, making them greener and, hence, sustainable. For instance, ESG considerations are incorporated in stress tests, implying that physical risks and climatic changes will significantly affect lending decisions made by banking sectors, raising questions about entrepreneurial intentions associated with sustainability.

Despite the above-presented reasons fueling entrepreneurial intentions to invest in sustainability, literature presents some limitations around ESG investing raising concerns around entrepreneurial intentions associated with sustainability. The following paragraph presented insights increasing such concerns.

One key concern is whether entrepreneurs or ESG-branded investors are genuinely committed to sustainability. This questions ESG branded investors' intentions because, from a paper documented by Kim and Yoon, it was evident that firms that became UN's PRI signatories exhibited a 4% surge in fund inflow in their first quarter despite doing nothing to advance their ESG scores (Kim & Yoon, 2020). This suggests that the signatories' behaviours or intentions were not committed to sustainability but simply attracting investment by becoming ESG signatories without advancing sustainability.

Given the differing insights on entrepreneurial intention towards sustainability, whether good or bad, research is required to uncover the factors that motivate entrepreneurs to invest or embrace sustainable investing. As a result, this study looks into the determinants of entrepreneurial intentions advancing sustainable investing in KSA, providing valuable ideas beyond academia for practical implications by policymakers, business development services, or entrepreneurs.

1.2. Research Problem

This subsection discusses the research problem mainly on the global community contesting KSA entrepreneurial intentions with regard to sustainability and how these impacts cross-border investments into KSA.

Whether KSA's government and entrepreneurs' intentions are geared towards sustainability remains a widely contested question. For instance, a 2023 online magazine by Teja titled "KSA's ESG profile: progress or PR?" confirms these contestations, affirming that in KSA, entrepreneurs' intentions with regard to sustainability balance a tightrope between economic opportunities and reputational challenges. There exists a growing concern in the international community on whether the KSA ESG profile is worth risking, with many multinational companies not settling for a definite answer (Teja, 2023). KSA has experienced increased foreign direct investments, with IMF in 2022 estimating cross-border portfolio investments into KSA's entities and debt at \$44 billion (Teja, 2023). While cross-border investments are suitable, the Fitch rating ascertained that political freedom and human rights limitations in KSA adversely impacted its ESG rating. Still, it rated the nation an A+ from an A, driven by the Vision 2030 reforms. While reforms surge sustainability are evident, KSA's intentions are often questioned, with most international players perceiving KSA as trying to make itself attractive for regional and global investors under cover of enhancing sustainability (Teja, 2023). Nevertheless, these views are widely contested, making entrepreneurs' intentions in KSA about sustainability a debatable topic.

While many banks globally are increasingly investing in green loans, KSA's banks provide a large percentage of their lending to the high-carbon sector, resulting in questions about their intentions about sustainability. Nevertheless, the government has increasingly invested in the diversification of the economy, focusing on sustainability and reducing reliance on oil. While these efforts promote ESG investing in the nation, inconsistent information on entrepreneurs' intentions with regard to sustainability deter marketing KSA as a strong ESG profile nation. As a result, a study is needed to provide comprehensive

and genuine entrepreneurs' intentions in KSA regarding sustainability. As evidenced by Kim and Yoon, many entrepreneurs become ESG signatories not to advance sustainability but to improve their reputation without doing anything to surge sustainability to obtain more investments (Kim & Yoon, 2020). Could this be the case in KSA? This study seeks to answer this question by investigating the determinations of entrepreneurial intentions in KSA with regard to sustainability.

1.3. Significance of Study

This subsection justifies conducting the study regarding what it will achieve, adding to existing literature and business knowledge, and informing policymakers. Mainly, it answers the question of why the study is needed.

This study extends beyond academics, providing stakeholders in KSA and policymakers some insights into the multifaced and complex association between entrepreneurial intentions and sustainability and how sustainable business practices impact financial performance. Concerning academics, the study bridges the gap in understanding the theoretical framework around sustainability and entrepreneurship and the intentions fuelling entrepreneurs towards sustainability, given evidence in the literature highlighting an insignificant association between sustainable business practices and financial performance. Understanding the determinants of entrepreneurship intentions towards sustainability is important to policymakers to ascertain if the intentions of entrepreneurs are genuinely geared towards sustainability. This study provides insights into some of the factors determining entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainability and ascertains whether KSA entrepreneurs' intentions are focused on sustainability or attracting ESG-conscious investors. With an understanding of the complex association between entrepreneurial intentions and sustainability and sustainability's impact on financial performance, policymakers can better formulate regulations to align business practices with sustainable business practices.

1.4. Research Questions

This subsection provides two research questions; one is the main research question, with the second question broadening the scope of the first research question. These research questions guide the study as its main aim is to answer them. The formulated research questions are as follows:

- I. What are the determinants of entrepreneurial intention to adopt sustainable business practices?

This primary research question points to the countless factors determining whether entrepreneurs in KSA plan to integrate sustainable practices within their ventures. From a single-trait perspective, socio-cultural influences, and contextual factors, the research will build an in-depth comprehension of why entrepreneurs within the Kingdom are more likely or less inclined towards sustainable business practices.

- II. Do these practices influence their enterprises' social and financial success?

The second research question broadens the scope of the first inquiry beyond entrepreneurial intentions to investigate more tangible outcomes of sustainable business practices. It questions the relationship between adopting sustainability and subsequent social success entrepreneurial ventures in KSA. The research looks into essential success indicators to determine how sustainable business practices affect performance, ultimately presenting practical intelligence on whether aligning entrepreneurship with sustainability goals has more significant consequences. These research questions are constructed in such a manner as to help the study go deep into various levels of complexity that are inherent in any significant research problem; these will guide this investigation toward an understanding of the relationship between entrepreneurial intentions and sustainability outcomes. In conjunction, they provide a broader understanding that includes not only the personal desires of entrepreneurs but also analyses their practical outcomes for achieving success in what would be considered ventures.

The research problem and questions set out in this chapter serve as a basis for an organised study on how entrepreneurial intentions interact with sustainable business practices within the unique settings of KSA. The following chapters will use a robust research approach to investigate these questions in detail, offering thoughtful conclusions that are not only valuable for theoretical purposes but also useful when further building the entrepreneurial environment in the Kingdom.

1.5. Study Objectives

- I. The main goal of this study is to determine among professional drivers affecting entrepreneurial intentions in the KSA fueling the focus on sustainable investing.

On this note is a comprehensive analysis of various dimensions of the driving forces influencing an entrepreneurial intention to incorporate sustainable business practices. This research attempts to develop a complete picture illustrating how different factors condition entrepreneurial intentions related to sustainability by studying unique features, sociocultural impacts, and contextual aspects. One thing that needs to be assessed as an inherent aspect of research objectives is evaluating the effects of sociocultural factors in establishing entrepreneurial intentions. As mentioned, KSA has a history and traditions full of colours, forming an idiosyncratic background that makes the understanding of how people's habits and attitudes towards values standards affect various leaders or entrepreneurs in their decision-making about sustainable investing. By unravelling these influences, the study can provide important information on how culture and entrepreneurship impact one another, particularly with sustainability in mind. Besides, this study examines how institutional context impacts entrepreneurial intentions about sociocultural elements. In this case, the institutional context covers the regulatory frameworks, government policies, and institutional structures that fuel or deter sustainable investing. Comprehending the peculiarities of institutional frameworks provides another

dimension of the factors impacting entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainable investing externally, as they do not have control over such factors.

II. The second goal is to determine if sustainable business practices impact financial success in KSA.

The study seeks to complement an investigation into the connection between intentions and actions by assessing the social and financial consequences of adopting sustainable business practices. The research analyses the correlation between sustainability and performance in general entrepreneurial ventures by looking at several critical success measures under systematic scrutiny. Such an assessment is a broad view of the practical implications of engaging entrepreneurial motives in line with sustainability objectives. Other than academic inquiries, the primary objective of such research is to provide practical knowledge for policymakers within business development services and entrepreneurs. The study aims to provide empirical, evidence-based, practical recommendations to inform people's decision-making in policy formulation, entrepreneurial support systems, and individual business strategies.

III. The third goal focuses on bridging the gap in knowledge on the connotation between entrepreneurship and sustainability.

Finally, this study aims to contribute significantly to particle knowledge in entrepreneurship and sustainability. By understanding the factors contributing to entrepreneurial intentions and their influence on sustainable business approaches, this research aims to develop knowledge that enhances theoretical frameworks that support both domains in order for people to gain a better insight into how competition between entrepreneurship and sustainability works. These objectives combine to inform the research direction with storytelling that touches on exploration, assessment, investigation, and evaluation. With these purposes, the study aims to provide significant insights into both academic knowledge and the real-life world of entrepreneurship and sustainability in KSA.

1.6. Thesis Statement

This subsection provides a statement that offers the central claim of the research. The statement has the main topic as a part and the controlling idea governing the basis of writing the thesis.

Despite KSA's entrepreneurial intentions, determinants focus on fueling sustainability to ensure investor attractiveness and promote the business image; sustainable business practices do not necessarily impact financial success in KSA.

1.7. Relevance and Benefits of the Study

The study on entrepreneurial intentions and sustainable business practices in the KSA holds significant relevance and benefits across various dimensions. Evident from current advancement, KSA is undergoing a transformative period with its Vision 2030. As a result, understanding entrepreneurial intentions toward sustainability is crucial for policymakers and business development services. This study provides insights into the multifaceted and complex connotation between entrepreneurship and sustainability, aiding in formulating regulations aligned with sustainable business practices. Moreover, the research contributes to academic knowledge by bridging gaps in theoretical frameworks surrounding entrepreneurship and sustainability. Practical implications for entrepreneurs and policymakers are derived, enhancing decision-making processes. Finally, the study addresses the international community's concerns about KSA's ESG profile and the long debate on whether sustainability practices in KSA are PR aimed only to attract ESG-conscious investors. By unraveling the determinants of entrepreneurial intentions, the research offers valuable information for investors assessing KSA's genuine commitment to sustainability.

1.8. Anticipated Methodology

To meet the research objectives and answer the study questions, this study adopts a mixed study approach encompassing quantitative and systematic literature review. The study's quantitative part aims to determine whether sustainable business practices impact financial performance. Besides, tests are also conducted to determine if management from a broader context has a significant association with sustainable business practices. A systematic review of literature is primarily used in this study to triangulate quantitative analysis findings and provide more insights into the determinants of entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainable business practices. This systematic literature review is conducted following PRISMA and PROSPERO guidelines.

1.9. Thesis Structure

This subsection provides an overview of the thesis, highlighting what is covered in each chapter.

Subsection 1.10 outlines the research limitations. These include limitations such as issues about data availability, potential biases, and even problems arising out of secondary analysis. To contextualise the study findings, it is critical to acknowledge these limitations to create transparency about the limits and boundaries of this research.

The second chapter will be a comprehensive review of relevant literature. This will entail researching current theories about entrepreneurial intentions and sustainable practices and how the two are related. The chapter aims to set a theoretical framework for the research and discover shortcomings in current knowledge. Literature focusing on entrepreneurship and sustainability within the KSA context will be given special attention.

The third chapter deals with research design and methods. A quantitative research design will be developed, justified, and tied closely to the objectives of this study. Secondary data analysis and systematic literature review approaches such as PRISMA and PROSPERO will also be discussed, as well as the dataset selection criteria. This chapter studies the factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions and their role in sustainable business practices.

The fourth chapter will be devoted to the consideration of ethical aspects. This covers data privacy, compliance with applicable regulations, and the application of research contracts to utilise confidential information. The chapter opens by emphasising how the research should be conducted with much integrity, ensuring that they remain compliant with all ethical standards and maintain the privacy of individuals whose data informs part or whole of their study.

The fifth chapter will detail what the research is likely to achieve. This includes identifying expected results based on the research questions and goals. This study intends to determine critical factors shaping entrepreneurial intentions and evaluate if sustainability directly or indirectly impacts financial and social outcomes. This chapter is a step-by-step guide to the study's implications for academia, business, and policy.

Chapter sixth is the results and discussion segment covering quantitative research findings and triangulations made from the systematic literature review to provide context to the findings. Besides, systematic literature review findings provide insight into the multifaced association between entrepreneurial intentions and sustainable business practices.

The last chapter is the conclusion and synthesis of the research. It presents significant findings and evaluates how such results might impact. What this research does is state towards its selection of choice that it assists sector-wide changes for better or worse with updates on the knowledge base. The chapter will also discuss potential avenues for future research, deriving from the limitations identified and areas requiring further studies.

The thesis remains analytically strict, ethical performance, and oriented towards making significant contributions about entrepreneurship to sustainability in KSA. The structure of the paper ensures that ideas flow logically, from theoretical foundations for literature review to practical implications and contributions observed in the conclusion.

1.10. Study Limitations

This subsection presents some of the limitations evident when completing the study. Personal and research methodology limitations and how they impact the research are discussed.

In addressing entrepreneurial intentions and sustainability in KSA's context, this research aims to untangle a maze of factors. Nevertheless, any scholarly work has limitations, and this research is not an exception to that rule either. One significant limitation is the double responsibilities of a full-time working life alongside academic endeavours and personal affairs. Given these multifaceted commitments, finding the time to write a thesis was difficult. The complexity of entrepreneurial and sustainability research requires intensive focus and intellectual involvement, with the limitation on time from external commitments that may be reflected in the scope and depth of study. Another limitation was the limited availability of current and updated data. Since the research methodology utilises data from credible sources, entrepreneurial activities and sustainability practices constantly change over time, which may result in outdated information. Since secondary data may not be as up-to-date as primary sources of information gathering, the study might fail to grasp current changes regarding entrepreneurial motivations or recent innovations within sustainable business approaches.

Again, establishing a smooth-running narrative and conducting comprehensive cross-source analyses was difficult as discrepancies in the methods of data collection, definitions, or measurement differ substantially between different sources. Using secondary data involves more dependence than the primary data collection method,

where researchers have complete control over how the study is conducted or was gathered. Any limitations or biases in the original data collection processes also affected this current study and introduced restrictions regarding interpretive possibilities and the generalizability of results. Despite the research being carried out with adherence to high ethical standards, there remain limitations when it comes to privacy and confidentiality. Due to the sensitive nature of some variables, particularly individual entrepreneurial activities, results relied on broader generalisations, not providing detailed insights without violating data owners' DUAs.

The limited time resulted in a review of a limited number of scholarly sources (41) despite the topic having numerous studies conducted in the past. Besides, purposive sampling was adopted due to limited access to many business databases. Adopting purposive sampling comes with possible researcher bias as decisions to choose a source for review are based on the researcher's decisions. Based on the insight, selection and confirmation biases were likely to impact the study adversely. Despite enhancing the study's focus, purposive sampling raised generalizability concerns as findings to a broader area may have been limited. Besides, unanticipated variables that might have impacted the study might have been overlooked by focusing mainly on the study variables. Despite the association between entrepreneurial intentions and sustainability being a global concern, the focus was kept only on KSA, and all the companies analysed were from the region, limiting the generalizability of the study to the world.

Moving forward to the limitations of the measures adopted, ESG scores as a measure of sustainable business practices face several limitations. One is that methods used to measure ESG scores are not standardised, implying that different rating agencies have different ESG scores for companies, implying that replacing the ESG scores of one rating company with the other would result in totally different results. Second, ESG scores are not measured based on sustainability initiatives but on a corporation's disclosure. As a result, companies that take part in "greenwashing" and enclose more on ESG practices were likely to have higher ESG ratings despite doing nothing towards sustainability. Besides, the weights assigned to ESG factors when determining ESG scores are subjective and vary among the rating corporations. Subjectivity is known to result in

discrepancies, likely resulting in inaccurate final ESG scores. Also, ESG scores are limited in scope when measuring sustainability as some aspects are difficult to quantify, resulting in overemphasising quantifiable aspects of sustainability. For instance, despite human rights, biodiversity, and community impacts being essential aspects of sustainability, they are not easy to quantify, limiting their integration into ESG scores computation.

Admission of these limitations is also consistent with scholarly ethics; more than that, it warns readers and interested parties about the possible limits within which this research might be conducted.

2.Literature Review

This is the second chapter of the thesis. This chapter comprehensively discusses how different authors have approached the topic area. The investigation will review all the relevant literature to address the research question and objectives.

2.1. KSA's Entrepreneurial and Sustainability Landscape

Entrepreneurship is an endeavour that reflects the urge that people have to create and sustain value among themselves. Countries such as KSA have gone miles ahead in entrenching an entrepreneurial spirit among their locals, but questions have always lingered around their sustainability when attracting foreign investors (Alsheikh, 2023). The intentions of most entrepreneurs, both within and outside, have been a subject of debate, mainly when the long-term benefits are far from sustainability (Chebbi & Ammer, 2022). Several people have questioned the intentions of some of the local and foreign entrepreneurs in creating a sustainable environment for the current and future generations when it is factual that hidden interests and desires push some.

Several investors are walking a tightrope when balancing between KSA's reputation for sustainability and the available economic and social opportunities. Debates have been directed at whether or not the country's sustainability agenda is worth the risk of several cross-border trades and how the same will impact its overall ESG goals. This is particularly the case because, since 2016, the level of FDIs in KSA has risen, with the country's debt and equity being sustainable (Reuters, 2023). The country's stock exchange market has experienced a marginal increase in activity thanks to cross-border traders' increasing desire and interest to invest in the many available opportunities (Boffo & Patalano, 2020). The International Monetary Fund (IMF) estimated that the country's equity will grow by \$50bn in 2025 through active FDI. The country's growing domestic

market has attracted several local and international investors, some of whom conflict with the interests of local lobby groups, particularly in areas of ESGs.

There has been mixed understanding of the term ESG, with some viewing it as the efforts of local authorities to foster a sustainable system for governance and environmental concerns. However, from an investment perspective, some Saudi human rights groups view it as a scapegoat by several cross-border players whose interest is only to maximise their returns at the expense of the locals. There is a general belief that since the KSA is an active and friendly commercial and investment country, some of the investors coming from countries with poor human rights records can take advantage of the existing KSA systems and entrench a climate of hostility (Teja, 2023; Princigalli, 2023). One of the critical elements of ESG is human rights and freedom of political association, which KSA has been accused of not withholding in the past. Several Saudi human rights defenders and political activists have been arrested and detained, while others have fled the country, according to Amnesty International. This goes against its stand on ESG and is why several players need clarification when key foreign investors get lucrative opportunities.

The following paragraphs will highlight some of the studies conducted on the country and how it has prioritised its ESG agenda at the FDI level. The reason is to understand the role played by FDIs in a country whose political and economic environment is often unstable and highly questionable on the global front.

A study by Knight Frank, a leading global real estate research firm, found that KSA is among the countries prioritising ESG as part of its sustainability agenda, mainly focusing on foreign direct investors. This study agreed with Reuters, which underscored the role of foreign direct investments in the Gulf region, particularly given its reliance on oil and gas. For instance, in the second quarter of 2023, KSA earned more than 6.2 billion Saudi Riyals (\$1.65b) from direct foreign investors who majored in the country's micro, medium, and small enterprises (Reuters, 2023). However, with the high inflow of funds, there have been issues around the country's quest to remain sustainable amidst societal and global concerns (Sadiq et al., 2022). Given the country's high reliance on oil, sustainable investing has been the focal point in most national discussions (Arab News, 2023; Al-

Jalahma et al., 2020). The attitude towards ESG has been two-fold in that there are those whose quest is to realise a sustainable environment for their quests. In contrast, others read malice into the main objectives of the foreigners and locals attracted to the country's investment environment.

The country's Ministry of Economy and Planning is committed to aligning its financial ecosystem with ESGs. It has been cautioning those out to taint its image by capitalising on existing gaps. Despite being primarily in a desert, the country's vision for 2030 is to transform its carbon footprint from much of its oil and gas industries by greening several public spaces to improve its air quality (Teja, 2023). The main concern, as was raised by Verisk Maplecroft, the leading global intelligence firm, affirms that KSA's average ESG rating is slightly higher than some of the world's developing economies, such as India and Brazil, with the outlook being 'stable.' Efforts have been channelled at business leaders to engage in responsible activities to make it more possible for the country to continue scoring higher on the global ESG ratings.

The following paragraphs will highlight the efforts by the KSA government to entrench democracy within its political, economic, and social systems even as it seeks to continue to market itself as the commercial hub of the Middle East. Efforts have been directed at government officials to abolish most of the draconian rules that existed in the country, making it less attractive for investment.

The KSA is predominantly an Islamic country whose laws are governed under the Sharia system. For many years, countries under this legal framework have been the subject of debate on aspects such as human rights, women, the environment, and politics (Umar et al., 2023). They often find it challenging to attract investors when their human rights and political records could be more questionable. However, as was observed by Pedersen & Partners, KSA has come a long way in shedding off some of its traditional governance systems and structures. Fundamental civil rights have been granted to women, which makes them more equal to men (Boffo & Patalano, 2020). According to the country's Ministry of Economy and Planning, this is a massive step towards creating and sustaining a stable investment environment, as every Saudi is deemed equal before the law.

Currently, more than 1.47 million Saudi women are in the active labour force, with their overall engagement in the country's social, economic, and political matters rising to more than 40% in 2022, according to Zentner (2023). The active participation of women in the country's governance systems has improved its ratings and perceptions among existing and potential investors, attracting more FDIs.

The pressure to allow women to engage in active, productive activities and live freely has borne fruits. Most foreign investors interested in the country's opportunities often perceive it as a hostile ground where, despite its Vision 2030, the likelihood of incurring losses is high (Zentner, 2023). The situation worsened upon the crown prince's discovery of the murder of writer Jamal Khashoggi in a Saudi consulate. The country's image and reputation were rapidly tarnished in the West, areas where most of the investors originate (Arab News, 2023). However, even as the KSA continues to market itself as the go-to investment hub in the Middle East, there have been debates on whether the changing legal, social, and political systems and structures will be sustainable in the long run (Arayssi et al., 2023). Several investors from Western countries are increasingly suspicious of KSA's attainment of its ESG goals, given its past profile and commitment to accommodating dissenting views and opinions.

In the following paragraph, attention will be given to the approach the KSA thinks best to achieve its ESG agenda despite different stakeholders' varying views and opinions. This aligns with an increasing number of foreign investors who call for a nuanced approach where the country strikes a perfect balance between its ESG expectations and the reality of increasingly global economic challenges. The question on the minds of several investors has always been: Should their investment decisions be based on ESGs or intuition to maximise returns or both?

Debates have centred on whether ESG has permeated the Saudi community. There have been variations in perceptions about women's rights and how they are treated at the workplace regarding duties assigned and pay (Almubarak et al., 2023). A study conducted by Almaqtari et al. (2023) revealed the many concerns raised on the impact of FDIs on KSA's ESG and the challenges likely to be experienced in the long run. However, the

nation's Ministry of Labor and Social Development claims that, the best way is to leverage the quasi-judicial systems to cement its approach to ESG and FDIs. According to the ministry, this will increase awareness among the locals and foreigners with scepticism about the country's investment environment. According to Abdelwahed et al. (2023), the government hopes that cultivating a healthy ESG culture will make it easier to attain most of its target goals and raise its standing in the global ESG index. Several ministries and the King Khalid Foundation have shown their support for this approach, hoping that by 2030, the country will have achieved much of its ESG objectives. Local and foreign companies have engaged in partnerships to create awareness of crucial ESG aspects, such as performance metrics, subsequently entrenching ESGs into decision-making.

2.2. KSA Vision 2030 Effect on Entrepreneurs and Sustainability

In this section, the literature covers the existing studies investigating the effects of KSA Vision 2030 on entrepreneurship and investors' sustainable development.

2.2.1. KSA's Vision 2030

Sustainable development goals (SDGs) are emphasised in KSA's Vision 2030 as largely dependent on entrepreneurship. The Kingdom's government has supplied all necessary resources, but the most crucial is assistance for entrepreneurs. According to Dhaliwal (2020), sustainable entrepreneurs must have a good company vision prioritising sustainable development. Perrini et al. (2020) state that sustainable entrepreneurs actively integrate sustainable practices into their business operations to enhance their company's efficiency and competitiveness in the social, economic, and environmental

domains. Prior research has attested to the importance of enterprise for sustainable development in accomplishing SDGs.

The following sub-section covers theoretical perspectives to investigate the linkage between entrepreneurship and achieving the SDGs in KSA to create a socially, economically, and environmentally sustainable society.

2.2.1.1. The Economic Aspect of Sustainability

The economic dimension pertains to efforts to enhance efficiency, lifestyle choices to mitigate energy and resource waste, and consumption habits that threaten biodiversity. Dhaliwal (2020) investigated how entrepreneurial exploration ensures that resources are allocated efficiently in a market economy and how various institutional configurations and cultural elements affect people's psychological susceptibility to alertness, enabling them to benefit from the exchange. Sergi et al. (2020) note that entrepreneurial integration processes accelerate efficient and high-quality economic growth. The author emphasises that entrepreneurship involves various integration processes, each of which has a unique and potential influence on economic development based on the circumstances. Due to this, Wennekers et al. (2020) discovered a U-shaped association between the rate of entrepreneurship and economic growth. If entrepreneurship and economic development are related in various nations, Wennekers et al. (2020) proposed that decision-makers should be aware of this link as it serves as a benchmark for their efforts.

2.2.1.2. The Social Aspect of Sustainability

Porter and Kramer (2020) explain that corporate sustainable development is primarily motivated by the belief that companies should contribute to society somehow. This ideology places a strong focus on licenses to operate, community and environmental governance, and the idea that businesses must obtain permission from governments, communities, and a wide range of stakeholders to work, and public image, a strategy many companies use to draw in clients. Seelos and Mair (2022) state that many companies contribute significantly to society through employment, better working conditions, attention to environmental concerns, and tax rates. Through implementing corporate governance initiatives, several major firms endeavour to create social benefits. İyigün (2021) acknowledged the importance of satisfying basic requirements by company owners and the positive societal impact on attaining sustainable development. As a result, Bogan and Darity (2022) emphasise that entrepreneurship is a potential development solution and a realistic alternative to unemployment and poverty. Dhaliwal (2021) points out that several variables may affect society, one of which is lowering the proportion of men and women of all ages who live in poverty. Attaining gender equality and creating social protection programs suitable for each country. Furthermore, enhancing or retaining the advantages for the national economy and reinforcing development initiatives to develop national ideals.

2.2.1.3. Environmental Aspect of Sustainability

Finding solutions that lead to environmental sustainability and attaining sustainability are very important to society. The development of some significant policy implications, according to Omri (2021), would enhance the quality of the environment globally and make clear how entrepreneurship affects ecosystem biodiversity and the environment.

One of the study's advantages is that it highlights the key variables influencing environmental deterioration and concentrates on the attention of scholars and decision-makers in looking for solutions that lead to environmental sustainability. According to Goel & Joshi (2020), ecological sustainability comprises implementing eco-friendly practices, managing the green supply chain, getting rid of garbage, reducing costs, and safeguarding the lives of future generations. Gafar, A. (2022) claims that companies and nations will employ resources to encourage plenty for the present generation while not compromising prospects for the future. Thus, this presumption helped to shape sensible economic policies that promote sustainable economic growth and enhance environmental quality. Hassan et al. (2021) conclude that ecological harm is decreased when governments have attained high economic growth.

2.2.2. KSA's Vision 2030 Impact on Entrepreneurship and Sustainability

Regarding the existing studies done by various authors, there was a positive impact of KSA Vision 2030 on entrepreneurial and investor sustainability in different regions of KSA. The evidence from the studies indicated that thorough green entrepreneurship, which was part of Vision 2030, created opportunities for green entrepreneurs to develop and scale innovative and sustainable solutions in their firms.

The Alzamel (2024) research looked at the KSA Vision 2030 elements that directly and indirectly affect the sustainability of investors and entrepreneurs in KSA through green entrepreneurial self-efficacy. The results indicate that the sustainability of entrepreneurs in the nation is positively and significantly impacted by green entrepreneurship. According to earlier research (Farooq, 2018; Reyad et al., 2019, 2020; Alvarez-Risco et al., 2021; Mia et al., 2022; Pennetta et al., 2023), these results align with this. These results show that Saudi investors and entrepreneurs adopt green business techniques as a sustainability aspect of their enterprises. To operationalise these measurements, Mamede et al. (2023) examined the determinants of green entrepreneurship by modelling

the preservation of capital in a KSA enterprise and emphasising the impact of system and network efficiency on enhanced economic arguments. Svensson and Wagner (2022) examined several approaches to improving sustainability by comparing the effect of finite resources and consumable inputs with green investments and business innovation in high-growth, high-innovation channels. These results support the hypotheses made by Sheth et al. (2022), who connected corporate goals like operational effectiveness and cost reduction to adopting greener, more effective industry solutions in KSA.

Similarly, the path analysis has demonstrated that green entrepreneurship contributes significantly to the sustainability of investors and entrepreneurs in the KSA. These results are in line with several other research, including those conducted by Li and Kang (2022), Zampetakis and Kanelakis (2010), Ghura et al. (2017), Ahmed et al. (2020), and Rizvi and Garg (2021). These results show no obstacles to entry into the KSA markets following the adoption of green entrepreneurship as part of the Vision 2030 agenda. Because of this, Nordin and Hassan (2019) highlight how there are several chances for green procurement and how in-demand green goods and services are. According to Mia et al. (2022), because people have access to information about green technology, they support green projects.

Likely by research conducted by (Deshpande et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2021; Belchior & Lyons, 2022; Lingappa et al., 2023). These results show that investors and entrepreneurs have made crucial contributions to their ventures' success due to the Vision 2030 strategy for green entrepreneurship. In this context, Eijdenberg (2020) contends that although they must confront the challenges associated with establishing and growing a business, they can modify their strategies for achieving sustainability. According to Deshpande et al. (2023), entrepreneurs in KSA want to advance their social status and accumulate wealth by seizing the chance to further their education and create new goods or company ideas. They contribute to the community's well-being where they live.

Moreover, the results of this investigation by (Nandanwar et al., 2022; Tuszynski & Stansel, 2022; Mrkajic et al., 2019; Liu & Liu, 2023; Arsawan et al., 2023; AlQershi et al., 2023). These results show that the tax structure in the Kingdom of KSA encourages

environmentally friendly corporate practices and that the government of the Kingdom provides attractive incentives and has ecologically conscious management. Consequently, Pacheco et al. (2022) point out that these should result in profits from market diversification and green business initiatives. Marshall and Samal (2022) say that these are effective methods for the KSA government to support green firms by offering straightforward product guidelines for green company operations. This is because the KSA is close to worldwide markets looking for green products. More precisely, Nandanwar et al. (2022) emphasise that the KSA government has established a fund for green entrepreneurship. As a result, loans are provided to assist eco-friendly projects and encourage funding for green entrepreneurship. Green company owners can seek low-interest financing with several available funding choices.

2.3. ESG Investing in KSA and Why Entrepreneurs and Investors Adopt

The section covers existing studies on why Entrepreneurs and investors in KSA adopt ESG investing and their intention toward sustainability. It addresses theoretical frameworks to elucidate the relationship between ESG investment practices and corporate sustainability outcomes. Furthermore, it explores the adoption of ESG principles in Saudi businesses, examining corporate governance and regulatory frameworks and how ESG affects performance in social and environmental sustainability. It also covers conflicting findings regarding the correlation between ESG practices and entrepreneurial intentions toward sustainability.

2.3.1. ESG Practices and Corporate Sustainability Theoretical Framework

This section presents four theories: stakeholder, agency, legitimacy, and signalling. To elaborate on the link between ESG investment practices and business sustainability performance.

2.3.1.1. Agency Theory

The reasons investors and entrepreneurs embrace ESG in their companies have been examined using several organisational theories. Four main ideas are emphasised in the literature on ESG disclosure: stakeholder, agency, legitimacy, and signalling theories. Fama et al. (2023) note a relationship between shareholders and management based on agency theory, characterised by shared interests. However, Jensen et al. (2021) point out that managers' interests do not always coincide with those of other shareholders. Therefore, companies disclose ESG factors to lessen this knowledge gap. According to Painter-Morland et al. (2021), a company's information environment is improved, and the knowledge gap between it and its shareholders is lowered when management discloses more ESG information, which is additional non-financial information.

2.3.1.2. Stakeholder Theory

Authors (Mohammadi et al., 2020; Katmon et al., 2021; Sadou et al., 2022) emphasize that stakeholder theory is necessary to preserve a strong and long-lasting relationship with stakeholders. According to Ramady and Saeed (2021), companies provide sustainability information on ESG initiatives to address the concerns and expectations of

important stakeholders, including the government, creditors, workers, suppliers, auditors, and the general public. Kramer et al. (2022) conclude that ESG influences organisational actions to satisfy the demands of different stakeholders and the public.

2.3.1.3. Legitimacy and Signaling Theories

Moreover, the legitimacy and signalling theories also commonly explain the adoption of ESG by investors and entrepreneurs as a means of corporate Sustainability. Girin et al. (2021) describe that an organisation must disclose additional social activities that underlie market shifts to demonstrate legitimacy. If an organization gains recognition for its social responsibility and is rewarded for it, the trustworthiness gap between it and society is increased. Katmon et al. (2021) note that signalling theory suggests that by aggressively pursuing ESG practices to create long-term value, a company may demonstrate to investors and other significant economic stakeholders that it is committed to these principles. According to Sulphery & Alkahtani (2021), in line with ESG strategy, senior management wants to better inform stakeholders and the board on the company ESG activities. According to Alshaikh et al. (2020), a business that does well in ESG might find it simpler to establish an excellent reputation for trustworthiness in the debt and capital markets.

2.3.2. ESG Investment Landscape in KSA

This section covers the adoption of ESG principles by entrepreneurs and investors in KSA firms. It focuses on the varying perspectives, both challenges and benefits, on the correlation between ESG practices and corporate sustainability outcomes.

ESG is often divided into three main aspects in Saudi businesses: social, environmental, and governance. The primary components of the social system are contributions, community welfare, human rights, health and safety, and workers. Reduction of emissions, product innovation, consumption of sources, recycling, and afforestation are all part of the environmental strategy. The governance plan includes applications that improve accountability, justice, transparency, and sense of duty.

Corporate governance and ESG requirements in KSA-listed firms are improved by a number of laws and regulations. Al-Janadi et al. (2021) noted that two of the most crucial components of sound corporate governance are openness and disclosure; putting these regulations into effect should raise the bar for corporate governance. According to the Saudi Capital Market Authority (2020), over the last 20 years, KSA has made great strides in corporate governance, starting with the publication of internal control standards (SCCG). which became compulsory for all Saudi-listed companies. Mohammadi et al. (2020) add that Saudi companies' ESG actions were given more weight by the government. The author notes that, in order for companies to enhance the social and economic conditions of the communities, the Ordinary General Assembly is required to develop a policy that strikes a balance between its objectives and those of the communities.

2.3.2.1. ESG and Environmental Sustainability Performance

According to Alshehri et al. (2022), a company's first duty is to its shareholders, and it will become less profitable and competitive if it engages in social and environmental projects since they incur additional expenditures. Environmental practices raise production costs and divert management and resources from the company's core competencies, which results in subpar financial performance. Al-Janadi et al. (2023) discovered a negative correlation between environmental performance and disclosure using a sample of KSA enterprises. Alwakid et al. (2021) expand on these arguments by pointing out that a high

level of disclosure, particularly natural, will reveal adverse information damaging companies' reputations. However, as stated by Alsayegh et al. (2021), well-crafted environmental rules may stimulate and drive innovations, such as the development of environmentally friendly technologies and improvements to the environment, which can reduce the costs associated with compliance and increase the competitiveness of businesses.

The studies by (Barbagila et al., 2021; Al-Alqam et al., 2020) demonstrate that environmental management methods used by firms improve Sustainability Performance. According to the authors by studying input and output indicators, businesses must build an environmental management framework to regulate and avoid ecological effects along the supply chain to integrate environmental management practices into the Environmental Sustainability Framework. Alharbi et al. (2022) state that the framework for environmental management considers a variety of inputs and outputs, including waste, emissions, and effluents, as well as inputs like water, energy, and materials. Girin et al. (2022) state that environmental performance is an outcome of environmental management that is often quantified considering the quantity of CO₂ emissions and lower emissions from carbon footprint. According to Mohammadi et al. (2023), cutting waste and CO₂ emissions entails improving resource efficiency and lowering pollution which as a result affects financial performance of the organization.

2.3.2.2. ESG and Social Sustainability Performance

Al-Janadi et al. (2023) state that the degree to which a business has implemented its social goals—such as those related to working conditions, health and safety, employee relations, health, inclusion, rights for humans, fair labour practices, community involvement, and philanthropy—is reflected in its social sustainability performance. According to Gholami et al. (2022), the high implementation costs of socially responsible policies surpass any potential tangible advantages. They are harmful to shareholders,

making them a misallocation and misuse of precious firm resources. Researchers like the authors [Mohammadi et al., 2020; Katmon et al., 2021; Sadou et al., 2022] have discovered a weak or negative correlation between the abovementioned factors.

Nonetheless, some research, like that of Bamahros et al. (2021), Al-Alqam et al. (2021), and Alharbi et al. (2021), shows that there is a positive correlation between ESG and social sustainability performance. These studies also contend that ESG practices offer several advantages, including improved efficiency and competitiveness, decreased operating costs and financial risks, and enhanced corporate reputation and consumer trust. Expanding on this point, Alwakid et al. (2021) contend that improved conditions for safety and health have internal advantages, such as a favourable effect on workers' devotion and allegiance to the organisation and motivation and morale. These factors may result in higher productivity and lower expenses for hiring and training new employees. According to Al-Janadi et al. (2023), enhancing company reputation and customer faith in brand value are the external advantages of ESG practices. These factors give the firm a durable competitive advantage.

2.4. Entrepreneurial Intentions Towards Sustainability in KSA

This section explores the existing studies that cover the relationship between ESG practices and Entrepreneurial Intentions toward Sustainability among enterprises in KSA. It explores conflicting findings regarding this correlation, investor perceptions, and the role of entrepreneurs in shaping sustainability dynamics.

The relationship between ESG and the sustainability performance of KSA enterprises has been extensively studied, impacting investors' and entrepreneurs' aspirations about Sustainability. A few reported a positive relationship. Others reported a negative association. However, several authors have not found any correlation between the Sustainability of the firms and their amount of ESG disclosure.

According to Gholami et al. (2022), as SMEs in KSA have different resources than bigger enterprises, ESG is of little benefit to entrepreneurs and investors who fund them. Because of this, Russo et al. (2020) identify a negative correlation between ESG and the Sustainability of SMEs in KSA. The author goes on to say that ESG is not considered a sustainability factor by investors and entrepreneurs who hope to fund SMEs in the nation. Comparably, Alwakid et al. (2021) indicate that ESG reporting on SMEs may negatively affect the firm's sustainability performance in KSA. However, Alsayegh et al. (2021) note that the connection is beneficial over the long term. Galdeano-Gomez et al. (2020) state that investors and businesses cannot disclose ESG information without the necessary resources. Schaltegger et al.(2021) stated that ESG reporting requires more financial, human, and transparent resources to expand investment. According to Barbagila et al. (2021), investors and business owners in KSA are most influenced by the cost of capital when adopting ESG practices. Alsayegh et al. (2020) suggest that investors should use international institutions for excellent ESG practices in their operations to achieve Sustainability over the long run.

However, Sulphey and Lkahtani (2021) noted a positive relationship between ESG and the sustainability performance of KSA's firms and forecasted how it will affect profitability. Ramady et al. (2022) note that through engaging in social uprisings and formal political processes, entrepreneurs and investors in the Kingdom of KSA (KSA) influence sustainability dynamics. For example, Idrissi (2021) reports that internal stakeholders in the FinTech industry in KSA are highly interested in the business's Sustainability and want to work for companies that have made significant environmental, social, and governance commitments. Green innovation capability has been found by Alsayegh et al. (2021) to benefit economic growth through environmental Sustainability.

Furthermore, some authors (Bamahros et al., 2021; Al-Alqam et al., 201; Alharbi et al., 2021) reported on a study conducted in KSA by PSB Middle East concerning ESG matters involving 200 applicants. The study found that fifty per cent of applicants needed to know whether all of their staff members fully understood the ESG framework, even though they already had one. According to Steinhöfel et al. (2022), ESG disclosures among KSA enterprises are positively correlated. Girin et al. (2020) also found that Saudi

organisations were conscious of Sustainability through the use of ESG criteria and that they had a responsibility to remain sustainable by lowering the risks associated with their Sustainability. In addition, Khaled et al.'s (2021) research showed that KSA's foreign investors significantly contribute to the country's GDP development and offered policy recommendations to make sustainability (finance and investment) more accessible in order to fulfill KSA Vision 2030.

2.5. Determinants of Entrepreneurial Intentions Towards Sustainable Business Practices

Attracting and sustaining an active entrepreneurial environment in the KSA depends on internal and external factors. The following subsections will discuss in detail both factors and how they influence the entrepreneurial intentions in KSA towards sustainability.

2.5.1. Internal Factors

The KSA became a member of the World Trade Organization in 2005, and since then, the country's investment climate has significantly changed. The government worked towards improving its image and brand on the global investment front, making it the go-to option for most investors. The internal factors likely to influence sustainable business practices include perception of risks, personal beliefs and values, and knowledge and skills (Sadiq et al., 2022). Additionally, brand image plays a significant role in shaping the perceptions others have towards the KSA, particularly on matters of sustainability. The country's economy, which depends on oil and gas, is strong enough to attract some of the world's best investors in critical sectors such as technology, energy, and business.

The following subsections will present an overview of some internal factors likely to attract more investors in the KSA and how they impact sustainability ESG attainment.

2.5.1.1. Perception of Risks

Risk is crucial to entrepreneurial success, particularly for businesses seeking to establish themselves in newer locations. An entrepreneur's approach to risks helps them determine the best strategies to take when engaging in sustainable practices (Princigalli, 2023). Unsustainable business practices are usually risky because of their adverse negative impacts on society and the environment. A manufacturing firm in the KSA, which has been accused of pollution for many years, can be used as a benchmark for an entrepreneur to understand the risks associated with environmental pollution. According to Sadiq et al. (2022), the long-term impact of these problems can likely shape their existing or upcoming business practices, leading to higher levels of sustainability. The riskier the outcome of a business idea, the lower the chances of an entrepreneur engaging in it and the higher their chances of realising a sustainable outcome.

2.5.1.2. Personal Beliefs and Values

Sustainability has been viewed by many as an internal motivation that pushes people towards better business practices. An entrepreneur with a high internal push to engage in sustainable practices will most likely earn the reputation of society and the government (Abdelwahed et al., 2023). In the case of the KSA, existing and new businesses are always assessed to determine their perceptions of the environment, governance, business practices, and society. Entrepreneurs with a firm belief in the continuity of their businesses are highly regarded by the Saudi government, especially if they focus on human rights, equality, and the environment (Massenbach, 2024). The underlying fact is

that entrepreneurs who believe in sustainable practices will entrench the same in their business, leading to better outcomes for themselves and society.

2.5.1.3. Knowledge and Skills

Entrepreneurship is a lifelong learning opportunity to navigate the environment in ways that benefit humanity. Entrepreneurs' knowledge and skills are crucial to realising sustainability in their business practices (Lyttle, 2022). The Saudi government has allocated resources to help local and foreign entrepreneurs understand more about sustainability and society's expectations towards businesses. Training centres have been opened across major towns to create awareness about the KSA's expectations of sustainable business practices and focal areas. This strategic move aims to minimise the costs associated with unsustainable business practices. Equipping businesses with the requisite knowledge and skills helps the government realise part of its Vision 2030 agenda and create a perception of a highly informed population on matters of sustainability, according to Samargandi et al. (2022). It also makes and sustains an entrepreneurial society with a strong inclination towards sustainable practices where innovative solutions to common problems are available (Mansour, 2023).

Another critical determinant is that for an entrepreneur to set foot in the country, they have to prove their contribution towards a healthier environment, protection of human rights and freedoms, and capacity to re-invest into other non-oil sectors. Large consumers, such as corporations, are encouraged to spend on green and sustainable energy, encouraging individuals to engage in similar practices (Abdelwahed et al., 2023). For instance, when foreign manufacturing companies go green, they easily influence their consumers to adapt to green consumption, which increases their sustainability standards and attracts more local and global entrepreneurs.

2.5.1.4 Brand Image

The Saudis understand that a strong brand image on the global front is a sure way of attracting more investors who, in turn, raise the country's economic fortunes. The government is the hub of several local, regional, and global business summits where entrepreneurs receive insights into potential investment areas. This is, however, amidst efforts by the Saudi government to change the century-long global perception of the country's approach to human rights, freedoms, and governance. The country seeks to blend traditions and modernity while giving women and youth equal opportunities (Al Helaly, 2023). Several women business leaders have been in the limelight, such as Sarah Al-Suhaimi, the head of Tawadul, one of Saudi stock exchange's largest companies, and Rania Nashar, a former CEO of Samba Financial Group, who made it to the Forbes 100 Most Powerful people. A vibrant local tourism industry has also helped reshape the KSA's reputation among the global community (Samargandi et al., 2022). These are among the many ways the government is shaping the local and international perception of freedoms and rights, which helps change its image and brand, particularly for foreign investors. Princigalli (2023) noted that with such structural changes, the country would be embraced by the global community, where more people will develop an interest in its resources, capacities, and opportunities.

2.5.2. External Factors

External factors make the KSA a preferred investment option for most foreign investors. The factors include political and economic stability in the Middle East, existing supporting technologies, availability of funds, and consumer awareness. Other external factors include prevailing cultural practices, government policies, and trade barriers. The

paragraphs below will discuss external factors contributing to the country's entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainable business practices.

2.5.2.1. Regional, Political and Economic Stability

The stability of the larger Middle East can affect the entrepreneurial ability of the KSA and the extent to which it attracts FDIs, subsequently affecting its sustainability. The economic and political stability of neighbouring countries such as Iraq, Yemen, and Kuwait determine the KSA's effectiveness in attracting and retaining foreign investors (Barbuscia et al., 2021). For instance, Iran has been characterised by numerous political instability and endless civil fights that create a negative perception of the Middle East region and deter investors from seeking opportunities in neighbouring countries such as the KSA. For this reason, the tourism sector in the KSA has been on a downward trend in the past five years due to the constant air travel interruptions from the Houthi attacks targeting most airports (Princigalli, 2023). The instability in the regional countries makes it almost impossible for KSA to market itself on the global front and, thus, deters it from realising its sustainable practices, among them the ESG objectives.

2.5.2.2. Existing Supporting Technologies

Most sustainable practices require the input of technologies to realise their objectives. Advanced technologies make it easier for entrepreneurs to fast-track processes, initiate new ideas, and compete in an ever-changing operating environment (Abdelwahed, 2022). The KSA has been the centre of technological development in the Middle East, and this is seen as a major factor driving entrepreneurial intentions. Zentner (2023) opined that the country has invested heavily in eco-friendly technologies that beckon more local and foreign investors to realise their business goals. Most companies are encouraged to adopt

solar and wind technologies as a push by the government to discourage high reliance on oil and gas due to their adverse environmental impacts. These approaches encourage entrepreneurs to engage in sustainable business practices with a mutual benefit to themselves and society.

2.5.2.3. Availability of Funding

One of the greatest determinants of entrepreneurial intentions in sustainable business is the availability of funds to realise their objectives. Governments work towards providing financial incentives to entrepreneurs as bait to attract them into specific areas of sustainability (Barbuscia et al., 2021). The KSA has made it easier for most local and foreign entrepreneurs to access funding through the country's vibrant financial system. Banks and other local financial institutions have made various products and services available to spur entrepreneurial spirit. It is easier for entrepreneurs who invest in sustainability to access funds to realise their objectives. According to Sadiq et al. (2022), this factor has attracted several local enterprises and renowned global brands to establish themselves in the country. The government uses numerous tech hubs and business incubators to welcome international entrepreneurs to partake in its investment potential. The government provides interest-free funding for entrepreneurs through the state-owned Saudi Industrial Development Fund, significantly boosting their business endeavours.

2.5.2.4. Consumer Awareness

Successful entrepreneurship is determined by the extent of the target market's awareness of sustainable business practices. The KSA has made efforts to ensure most locals are aware of and demand sustainable products and services, which helps address most of their concerns. The high level of consumer awareness of specific goods and services

assures entrepreneurs of the sustainability of their businesses and maximum support from both the government and the locals (Clément et al., 2023). However, some entrepreneurs view this as an advantage to take charge of the markets at the expense of their consumers and other players. For example, customers in the KSA are conscious of the environmental effect of the oil and gas sector. For entrepreneurs, realising sustainability will only depend on their efforts to address these concerns. Consumer awareness is a strong factor that shapes the approaches taken by entrepreneurs to enter and sustain themselves in new markets (Boffo & Patalano, 2020). In this context, an FDI from the West should navigate what the local Saudis know and prefer about their products and services before establishing themselves in the economy.

2.5.2.5. Existing Cultural Practices

The existing Culture in the KSA largely determines the entrepreneurial intentions toward creating and sustaining stable businesses. Many FDIs are attracted to a country whose Culture respects the needs and expectations of locals and foreigners and where every person is free (Dorfleitner et al., 2015). For many years, the Culture in the KSA has been retrogressive to deter women from actively engaging in community affairs. This becomes a significant concern for most FDIs whose interests go beyond commercial gains. Therefore, cultures where some members are under certain restrictions may not be fully open to foreigners, affecting the degree and level of business success (Boffo & Patalano, 2020). However, the launch of Vision 2030 in 2016 was the genesis of a series of events that opened the country's freedom space, which has since seen several laws repealed to allow every societal member to enjoy their rights. As of 2019, the KSA's Culture has undergone significant changes, with women no longer under restrictions (Lyttle, 2022). This is a strategic move to attract more foreign investors as their perceptions about the KSA and freedoms will likely change. More investors coming into the country will assure locals of sustainability in the long run as the government seeks to transform the country's Culture to be more accommodating.

An entrepreneur determined to enter the KSA's market needs more control over the existing local cultures and will be required to align their business models with existing ones. For instance, people in the KSA do not consume pork, alcohol, or second-hand goods such as clothes. Existing cultural restrictions mean entrepreneurs have alternatives to engage the Saudis other than what their culture bans or abhors. Those who need to observe and embrace the country's fundamental cultural practices will find gripping the locals in sustainable business practices challenging. This move can result in legal challenges.

2.5.2.6. Government Policy

The KSA government has assumed a series of policies to create and sustain a business-friendly environment for locals and foreigners. Alwakid et al. (2020) observed that the growth of the Saudi investment community is primarily due to the rise in technological applications and the availability of funds in the form of grants and other incentives to spur businesses. The move has seen more established companies nationwide, largely contributing towards its GDP, with KSA being the second-largest economy in the Middle East after the UAE. An article published in the Entrepreneur titled Why KSA is the Future Frontier for Global Entrepreneurs recognises and appreciates the role of the country's government in strengthening businesses through its policies. A passion for change drives most local entrepreneurs, thanks to the government policy that sought to open the country to the external world through innovation (Al Helaly, 2023). The move has attracted great global attention, which aims to increase the number of investors in the country, thus achieving its business sustainability intention in the long run.

2.5.2.7. Trade Barriers

Regional trade barriers have been known to influence the free flow of goods in the Middle East, potentially affecting the level of business activities between the respective countries and the rest of the world. For instance, entrepreneurs seeking to trade in certain goods and services such as pork, alcohol, and narcotics may not gain entry into most Middle Eastern markets. The barriers to trading in such products are established to uphold the regional values and cultures that primarily affect trading (Sadiq et al., 2022). Trade barriers create the perception of a closed and unpredictable market, which deters many potential investors from a given region (Sadiq et al., 2022). However, as a member of the WTO, the KSA has continued to assure its significant partners, such as the US, of its intentions to liberate its markets so that it does not suffer the negative consequences of existing market barriers (Dorfleitner et al., 2015). Barriers have affected key areas of intellectual property rights protection, payment, and performance, leading to more disputes between authorities and traders. The existence of trade barriers is a sure way of closing up the Middle East to the outside world, which can hinder the realisation of sustainable businesses and, thus, impact the country's ESG objectives.

2.6. CSR Impact on Financial Performance

This section focuses on a comprehensive examination of the theoretical framework surrounding CSR and financial performance, followed by an analysis of the factors influencing CSR practices in KSA. Subsequently, it also explores studies supporting positive, no significant, and negative relationships between CSR and financial performance, providing a well-rounded understanding of the topic in the context of KSA.

Issa (2021) defines CSR as a type of corporate self-organisation that seeks to accept the company's responsibility for its actions towards society by positively having an effect on

stakeholders, communities, workers, consumers, the environment, and the society through its operations. Carroll (2021) says businesses increasingly realise that they may outperform their rivals by leveraging social responsibility. Companies have created CSR business plans to obtain a competitive edge. Maretno (2022) also corroborates these claims, pointing out that many companies prioritise CSR initiatives. They include these actions in their plan and use their resources to facilitate the social and environmental effects while improving the communities around them.

Overall, there are three categories of studies on the relationship between CSR actions and financial performance: those that support a positive link, those that deny any correlation and those that support a negative one.

Numerous studies highlight the detrimental relationship between financial success and CSR, highlighting the need for corporations to prioritize their consumers' needs. Alshareef & Sandhu (2020) contend that businesses should focus on achieving their primary goal, which is to increase shareholder profits, as this will be sufficient to satisfy their legal requirements under laws and regulations. As a result, the author claims that CSR, moral obligations, and donations all reduce shareholder profits. According to Masoud and Vij (2021), CSR initiatives that deviate from legal and financial duties can have a negative effect on shareholder values and profit maximization in addition to having a negative influence on stakeholder revenues.

However, other research rejects the idea that connection exists between CSR and financial performance. According to McWilliams and Siegel (2020), financial performance and CSR do not significantly correlate. Other research, on the other hand, reveals positive or negative relationships due to flaws in the study design. Selling and Webb's (2021) research, which finds that, when time-series effects are taken into account, there is no statistically significant association between CSR and business financial success, lends weight to these views. It is contended that if the study models are more intricately developed, the positive association demonstrated in earlier work would diminish. They claim that CSR cannot improve the financial success of corporations.

On the other hand, many research studies show a positive association of how CSR affects businesses' financial success. Positive correlations are attributed to those that highlight the social function of corporations and are grounded in stakeholder theory. Businesses have increasing societal obligations in tandem with their growth in size and power. Stakeholder theorists like Freeman (2023) contend that companies are more than just profit-making entities; they also have societal responsibilities, such as meeting the requirements of their stakeholders and trying to be accepted by the community. Essentially, they think CSR initiatives reduce stakeholder and company conflicts of interest while boosting profits and company value. By using contribution expenditure as a stand-in for CSR spending, Choi et al. (2019) conducted an experimental analysis of the beneficial relationship between CSR activities and financial performance. The author concluded that improved firm reputation may be achieved through the use of CSR, an intangible investment type.

2.6.1. CSR and Financial Performance in the Context of KSA

This subsection covers factors influencing CSR in KSA and case studies on the relationship between CSR actions and financial performance in the context of KSA: those that support a positive link, those that deny any correlation and those that support a negative one.

2.6.1.1. Factors Influencing CSR Practices in KSA

This subsection covers existing studies to explore two key factors, Profitability and firm size, that currently influence CSR practices in KSA. It discusses how profitable businesses usually provide the public access to more social information and how larger

firms are more inclined to incorporate CSR information into their yearly reports. due to their ability to afford associated costs.

Numerous Saudi enterprises are starting to see the benefits of adopting ethical business practices, as per Issa (2021). According to the author and the media, there is a gap in the public's and consumers' perceptions of CSR. Aside from that, CSR has improved in KSA. The primary industries with higher levels of CSR activity include banking, retail, and industry. Although CSR differs throughout KSA businesses and sectors, about 66% of listed corporations have CSR in annual reports. Alotaibi (2020) highlights that most companies integrated their CSR into their human resources and community engagement initiatives. According to Ala'Eddin et al. (2022), CSR disclosure in listed Saudi companies positively and significantly correlates with profitability and company size.

2.6.1.1.1. Firm Size

Numerous studies (A-Janadi et al., 2022; Basuony, 2022; Alturki, 2021; Giannarakis, 2015) have found that larger businesses usually provide more voluntary information to the public. The explanation for this outcome is that large corporations attract the attention of external stakeholders such as the government, media, trade groups, and consumers because they are more conspicuous (Gilon et al., 2020). However, a few studies (Hussainey et al., 2021; Al-Moataz & Hussainey, 2012; Saleh et al., 2020) have not discovered a connection between voluntary disclosure and an organisation's size. Prior research on the relationship between KSA firm size and voluntary disclosure has shown a positive association. Basuony (2022) and Alturki (2020) have shown a favourable correlation between voluntary disclosure and the firm's size. Larger Saudi businesses are likely to post information regarding CSR in their yearly reports, according to Alofi (2020), since they can more easily afford the associated reporting costs. Thus, a positive association exists between market capitalisation and the degree of CSR.

2.6.1.1.2. Profitability

Profitable businesses reveal more social information to the public to justify their existence. Previous studies have proposed a favourable association between voluntary disclosure and Profitability (Al-Moataz & Hussainey, 2022; Al-Janadi et al., 2023; Kansal et al., 2019). For instance, some research (Aljifri et al., 2014; Barac et al., 2014) did not detect any link. Belkaoui and Karpik (2022) substantiate that management's awareness is the fundamental reason for a favourable association between Profitability and corporate social responsibility disclosure. Prior studies on the relationship between voluntary disclosure and Profitability in the KSA have produced contradictory findings. While Said et al. (2009) and Basuony (2014) find no link, Al-Moataz and Hussainey (2022) show a favourable correlation between voluntary disclosure and Profitability. Alotaibi et al. (2022) found that profitable KSA companies are likelier than less profitable companies to include more CSR details in their annual reports.

2.6.1.2. Studies on KSA's CSR Impact on Financial Performance

The following subsection presents some study findings highlighting CSR lacking and having positive and negative impacts on financial performance.

2.6.1.2.1. Studies Supporting Positive Relationship between CSR and Financial Performance

Using zakat as a stand-in for CSR, Al-Malkawi and Javaid's (2020) study investigated the connection between CSR and financial success. The research uses a set of control

variables, including size, leverage, and age, and assesses performance using market Price-to-Book Ratio (PB) and accounting Return on Equity (ROE). Over ten years, from 2013 to 2018, the study looked at 107 non-financial enterprises listed on the KSA stock market. The study's findings demonstrate a substantial positive correlation between financial performance and CSR. A study by Alotaibi (2021) implies that zakat adds societal positivity to a company's worth and Profitability. As a result, in Islam, CSR (Zakat) benefits financial performance by helping society. Furthermore, from an Islamic standpoint, Al-Malkawi and Javaid (2020) support the stakeholder thesis that businesses operating in Islamic economies can successfully apply the fundamental Shari'a Law of paying Zakat to implement corporate social responsibility programs.

Another study by Habbash (2021) found a positive correlation between financial performance and CSR. In the author's words, the study's objective was to identify KSA's CSR disclosure level and its possible impact on company value and financial performance. An examination of 267 Saudi-listed companies' annual reports from 2018 to 2020 was conducted using manual content analysis and regression analysis. Tobin's Q was a market-based proxy for business value, while an accounting-based proxy for financial success was ROA. According to Habbash (2021), a higher level of social transparency may enhance company value. Furthermore, Abdulhaq and Muhamed (2022) discovered that institutional and state ownership, role duality, and company age all favourably impact financial performance, but no governance variable impacts firm value.

2.6.1.2.2. Studies Finding No Significant Relationship between CSR and Financial Performance

Dkhili and Dhiab's (2021) study investigated the impact of CSR on financial performance within the Saudi business sector. Results indicate no correlation between financial performance as evaluated by ROA and social responsibility, but a positive correlation is

seen when ROE measures financial performance. Al-Samhan (2023) concludes that no correlation exists between social responsibility and financial success when control variables like size, risk, and industry are included. Similarly, according to Ross's (2021) study, various factors might modify the association between financial performance and social responsibility. The author says that while there may be sporadic evidence that social responsibility influences financial success, the challenge of quantifying social responsibility may obscure any potential relationship between the two. According to some authors (Maignan et al., 2021; Heo et al., 2021; Badkook et al., H. 2019; Aupperle et al., 2021), it is not feasible to hypothesise the presence of a stable link between the two variables in this context because the relationship between social responsibility and financial success is so intricate and indirect.

2.6.1.2.3. Studies Indicating a Negative Relationship between CSR and Financial Performance

According to some research, there is a negative correlation between financial success and CSR. In this section, the studies reviewed showed a negative correlation between CSR and an organisation's financial performance. This could be due to financial misappropriation in organisations where considerable resources have been allocated to CSR programs that do not immediately generate money.

A study conducted by Muthuswamy and Yunusova (2023), which included 115 KSA stock exchange-listed companies, provided a complex link between CSR and CFP that shows that CSR negatively influences an organisation's financial performance. Comparable studies by (Ala'Eddin et al., 2020; Jamali et al., 2021; Muthuswamy & Yunusova, 2023) claim that CSR initiatives violate shareholder interests by raising expenses above and above the company's initial management initiatives. Since businesses must grow the economy and generate jobs, the authors contend that the fundamental responsibility of a firm is to uphold its original objective of generating profits for its shareholders.

Alshareef and Sandhu (2021) looked at the relationship between CSR and KSA firms' financial success in another study. The price-earnings ratio and CSR performance were shown to be negatively correlated by the study. The company's financial performance was assessed using the earnings-price ratio in addition to other general performance metrics. CSR is starting to negatively impact an organization's financial line. Alotaibi, 2021; Issa, 2021; Dkhili et al., 2019) conducted research on the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and financial success. Their reasoning was based on agency theory. They argued that managers who overspend on CSR projects in order to advance their careers or satisfy personal agendas diminish the value of the firm by driving up agency costs.

2.7. Sustainable Business Practices and Financial Performance Quantification

Several criticisms have been labelled against countries or organisations working towards realising their ESG objectives. According to Dremptic et al. (2019), many view the approach as a strategy organisations or countries use to remain competitive and relevant in a world of constant and unpredictable changes. The following paragraphs will review some of the criticisms of using ESG scores to measure and assess the sustainability of business practices, with a focus on the KSA.

The KSA is among the countries leveraging its ESG agenda to attract more foreign investors while strengthening the existing ones. However, with the approach of using ESG scores, many people still need to determine whether the country is living up to the main expectation of this approach- greenwashing (Kotsantonis & Serafeim, 2019). Several stakeholders within the KSA argue that attaining higher ESG scores will benefit the country (Atkins et al., 2022). However, it could also be used by the West to sway it from addressing real internal concerns. In the UK, for instance, several investors disapprove of using ESG scores, with a survey conducted by Edelman noting that three-quarters of foreign investors need to be more trusted to achieve their ESG goals. Therefore, the

actual impacts of ESG cannot be felt in the KSA when aspects of diversity and inclusion still rock its existing systems and structures.

Most ESG scores are complicated and almost impossible to achieve, particularly for countries whose economies primarily rely on oil and gas. The KSA is among the global economies anchored heavily on the oil industry, whose environmental cannot be ignored. In most cases, environmental, sustainability, and governance aspects are interrelated, and questions have been raised about using a single score to achieve or measure a certain threshold (Dorfleitner et al., 2015). In the KSA, several priority areas include human rights, freedoms, and inclusion, and relying on ESG scores benefits certain regions at the expense of others. For instance, ESG scores may focus on KSA's approach to the environment while isolating other critical aspects of law, human rights, and freedom for women. Therefore, the ESG scores satisfy the needs and interests of most foreign investors in KSA at the expense of other local stakeholders, particularly women.

ESG scores vary in their use, assessment, and ratings. For instance, the ESG scores for the KSA on a given topic, such as the environment, may differ from those used by the US or France. A standardised ESG measure that cuts across different regions needs to be improved to understand better the identified variables (Rajesh & Rajendran, 2019; Sadiq et al., 2022). Additionally, agencies such as Bloomberg and S&P Global will provide different rating scores for the same factors in the country. This increases confusion on the correct measure and how it can be interpreted based on the variables under review (Clément et al., 2023). In other instances, those behind the ESG scores can manipulate the values to favour their desired outcomes. Therefore, a country such as the KSA can score highly on governance even when the case may be otherwise.

The real impact of ESG scores on society is still debated among scholars and policymakers. Studies conducted by Diez-Cañamero et al. (2020) have attributed the positive success of societies to ESG scores, while Lyttle (2022) failed to link the two, mainly when the rating agencies produce varying outcomes. In the case of the KSA, it can score highly on environmental matters due to the policy by the authorities to shift away from internal combustion vehicles to electric. However, the ability of such scores to

address the locals' real needs is still a subject of debate (Kotsantonis & Serafeim, 2019). The actual scores are not meant to solve some of the critical societal and environmental issues but rather meet investors' existing and emerging needs to pursue their commercial goals.

Some investors are yet to realise the maximum benefits of using ESG scores on their invested capital. The University of Chicago conducted a study whose findings revealed no relationship between the performance metrics of high and low sustainability funds. Other studies have proved that companies with responsible investors scored low on specific aspects of ESG and, thus, experienced more financial challenges. According to Clément et al. (2022), the general verdict is that ESG scores are meant to portray a business or country as highly compliant and sustainable in the long run when, in a real sense, the opposite effect is felt. Businesses often handle the real benefits from an environmental and commercial perspective only in the short run. At the same time, countries such as the KSA use the scores to market themselves globally. The essence is for countries to reshape and rethink their approaches to ESG scores to maximise their benefits and positively impact the lives of their locals.

The paragraph below provides an outlook of the KSA and how the ESG scores have helped shape its global outlook. This is after Fitch Ratings, one of the world's leading rating agencies, gave the country an "A+" score with its outlook largely "Stable."

The impressive KSA's ratings were primarily based on its balance sheet strength, rising but low debt, a more accessible fiscal policy, and a vibrant non-oil economy. The country's vision for 2030 equally plays a significant role in its quest to maintain a positive global image in the ESG scores with several ambitious mega projects in the oil and non-oil economies (Sadiq et al., 2022). Additionally, the country plays a significant role in stabilising the larger Middle East region, which, according to Clément et al. (2023), has increased investor confidence, a crucial factor in FDI. On the political front, the country has embraced democratic principles, with the rule of law taking precedence. There are fewer cases of corruption in the country, making it one of the reasons FDIs are attracted

to its opportunities. However, with such impressive scores, a lot still needs to be done for the Saudis to realise the maximum benefits of any FDI.

Measuring the financial performance of companies using both ROA and ROE possesses significant benefits and challenges. The paragraph below will evaluate the advantages and limitations of using ROA to measure financial performance and compare it with ROE.

Investors using ROA to decide the nature of their investment decisions rely on the efficiency with which companies maximise their assets to generate revenues. For instance, in the case of the KSA, most FDIs will leverage the country's infrastructure network and how they can add value to their invested capital. The more value they derive from their investment, the higher their chances of tying their funds into the country (Eldaia, 2020). Ultimately, the KSA is more likely to score higher on its ESG objectives, attracting more investors. Additionally, ROA is a measure of the management's capacity to allocate resources. Barauskaite and Streimikiene (2020) noted that the metric reveals how the leadership acquires and apportions most resources. The KSA, being rich in oil and gas, quickly catches them at lower costs, and by selling in other countries, its GDP has been steadily rising. It is an approach likely to see more FDIs interested in its other resources, leading to a more vibrant economic model.

However, the only challenge with relying on ROA is that most metrics are far from reality. Casielles (2019) observed that some investors are interested in knowing how a company generates its revenues and future management policies and plans, if any. This is, however, not the case, as most companies continue to decrease their asset volumes in the post-pandemic world. Countries have yet to recover from the pandemic's after-shocks fully, and those reporting higher ROAs may be farfetched.

The strength of a company relies heavily on the strength of its equity. A higher ROE implies a company ready to realise its going concerns due to the likelihood of enjoying a larger market share occasioned by higher profits (Galankashi & Rafiei, 2021). Investors are more cautious with companies recording lower ROEs as their likelihood of winding up is higher in the long run (Princigalli, 2023). Therefore, in the case of the KSA, higher ROEs reported by the local firms indicate a favourable economy with higher returns in the long

term. It becomes easier to negotiate with such companies who, upon establishing themselves in the economy, can help propel its ESG agenda while growing and expanding its GDP at the same time. However, caution is always given when using ROE, as high values may not indicate a company's performance (Manogna & Mishra, 2021). It is an indicator likely to change over time with varying accounting standards, and investors relying on these metrics are more cautious with their investment decisions.

3.Methodology

This chapter presents the research's philosophical and methodological approaches adopted in studying the determinants of entrepreneurial intention toward embracing or avoiding sustainability in KSA, following positivism and relativism-research philosophies. Besides, this section also clarifies why an exploratory single case study combined with grounded theory was a preferred research design and illustrates how the developed analysis enabled the formulation of multiple theories based on the study findings. In addition, this chapter looks into ways to guide the researcher to act ethically and maintain the quality of data in a mixed study on the research topic.

3.1. Research Overview

This section provides some of the reasonings behind the researcher's quest to complete the research on the topic, particularly in KSA, and the questions to be answered.

At the stage of progress and environmental responsibility issues, KSA is standing at one critical crossroads. The Kingdom, known for a long time because of its tremendous oil fields, is moving towards an eco-friendly future powered by emerging green, inventive thinking. This raises concerns about whether such entrepreneurial efforts are geared toward sustainability or the need to make KSA's market attractive for ESG investing, given its growing scale in recent years. When completing this study, such questions arose in the researcher's mind: What motivates people to choose this track? What internal and external factors force them to establish sustainability at the core of their undertakings? This question guides the research journey marked by the analytical compass wandering from quantitative analysis and an unwavering passion for discovering forces that can harness aspirations towards becoming agents of entrepreneurship in KSA. There are two interlinked research questions to guide this journey presented below.

- I. What are the determinants of entrepreneurial intention to adopt sustainable business practices?
- II. Do these practices influence their enterprises' social and financial success?

Evident from the questions, the study aims to shed light on the factors that tend to push people toward the green side of entrepreneurship. Is it a burning conviction in environmental preservation? This question needs further research as mixed findings are evident in the association between CSR and financial success in different companies. Companies that take the environment seriously emphasise the effective handling and management of waste products, thereby getting risk management benefits from sustainability. On the other hand, Kim and Yoon (2020) ascertained that some ESG signatories are not genuinely for sustainability but sing as a party to attract ESG-aligned investors. That said, entrepreneurship intentions towards embracing sustainability might stem from an acute awareness of the approaching business opportunities in the rapidly growing sustainability sector. It is an exciting blend of altruism and economic rationality, recognising that green enterprises can have benign impacts on the planet while profiting. To get through this highly debatable landscape, the researcher explores the vastness of pre-existing data and tries to route the way with the sheer force of secondary analysis to settle the controversies on the study topic.

3.2. Research Philosophies

Research philosophy forms the basis of assumptions taken to complete a study. When conducting different studies, researchers adopt varying approaches based on the nature and knowledge they wish to acquire. Their main functions in a research paper include but are not limited to method facilitation, demystifying, and informing. Four major research philosophies exist: realism, pragmatism, interpretivism, and positivism. Addressing research philosophy in this study implies that the researcher was aware of personal prevailing beliefs and assumptions guiding the study. Practical implications impact

research philosophy choices. This study adopts a quantitative study, making positivist research philosophy the most appropriate, unlike interpretivism, which is often adopted for qualitative study. Positivist philosophy applies to this study since the research is highly structured, involves analysis of continuous numeric data, and utilises a large sample size.

Unlike interpretivist philosophy, positivist philosophy emphasises empirical evidence and maintains objectivity, which is the main focus of the quantitative aspect of this research. Besides, ESG and financial performance are measurable phenomena, aligning with the positivist research philosophy. Positivist philosophy also allows exploration of causal associations, making it suitable for this study as one of its aims revolves around drawing inferences. Besides, this study aims to provide a generalisable body of knowledge, making it appropriate to adopt a positivist research approach. Biasness impacts the reliability and validity of a study. Given its commitment to neutrality, this study adopts a positivist philosophy, thereby ensuring unbiased results. Given its rigorous framework, the researcher chose positivist philosophy fostering scientific exploration of the complex and multifaced association between entrepreneurial intentions and sustainability and the impact of these practices on financial performance.

3.3. Research Design

This subsection presents research designs and their significance in this study, after which a recommended research design is selected and discussed.

Choosing a research design is an important choice that influences the methodology and results of any study. There are several compelling reasons why quantitative research design is an appropriate and advantageous approach to investigate entrepreneurial intentions and sustainability in KSA. Among the significant research designs selected in this study were quantitative, systematic literature review, and mixed research designs. Quantitative research is superior in giving a structured and objective measurement of variables. Defining the adoption of sustainable practices, establishing financial success

indicators, and determining entrepreneurial intentions in this approach allow for the exact quantification of these factors. Standardised metrics guarantee transparency and validity in measuring complex interactions between variables, enabling rigorous analysis and comparison of the findings. Quantitative research design can also be ideal for establishing causality between variables. Through the statistical analysis, it is possible to establish how entrepreneurial intentions favour or hinder the adoption of sustainable business models and reciprocally affect businesses socially and financially. This causal inference capacity improves the study's potential to make rich and meaningful conclusions about the dynamics of entrepreneurship on sustainability.

On the other hand, despite the superiority of quantitative study in allowing the drawing of inferences, it exhibits limitations such as failure to provide the context of the analysed data, a shortcoming that systematic literature review solves. A systematic literature review aids in contextual analysis, providing insights into factors influencing entrepreneurial decisions to embrace or deter efforts toward sustainable investing. For instance, relevant to this study, with a systematic literature review, investigations can be made on how institutional context, economic, and cultural factors impact decisions or attitudes toward sustainability, thereby identifying barriers and motivating factors. Besides, this study aims to develop theoretical frameworks, making it necessary to explore perspectives explaining the associations between entrepreneurial intentions and sustainability determined from a systematic literature review. Finally, a systematic literature review is essential in validating the findings determined from the quantitative study by providing a deeper understanding of why the results are what they are and their implications. Based on the insight, while the quantitative study is superior in this study, its success should be supplemented with a systematic literature review to improve its validity.

Having presented the relevance of quantitative and systematic literature review research design to this study and how they complement each other, the following paragraphs provide insights into why mixed research design was selected.

The mixed approach was preferred over the individual approaches to provide a comprehensive study, allowing the drawing of inferences and theory development. With

a mixed approach, triangulation was made easy with quantitative results, which were not expected to be validated using systematic literature review findings. As stated earlier in the introduction, the association between entrepreneurship intentions and sustainability is multifaced and complex. Combining quantitative and systematic literature review approaches is necessary to understand the associations better. While the quantitative part of the study utilises credible data sources, including governmental databases, industrial findings, academic studies, and international organisations, the systematic literature review part of the study adopts PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) and PROSPERO (International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews) guidelines, further improving the study's reliability.

The quantitative parts of the study cover descriptive and inferential statistical analysis, with the descriptive analysis providing insights into sustainable practices in KSA as measured by ESG scores. On the other hand, the correlational research design is adopted to determine the association between entrepreneurial intention and sustainable practices and whether sustainable practices have financial implications for firms. Considering the quantitative data collected is of numerical and continuous data type and data modelling, respectively, a linear association is assumed to exist between the dependent and the independent variables, allowing the development of a regression model to determine that variability in financial outcome explained by sustainable business practices in KSA. Specifically, when investigating the impact of sustainable business practices on financial support, the effect of ESG score on a firm's ROA and ROE are investigated. Once the findings are determined, a systematic literature review is conducted to justify whether entrepreneurial intention in KSA is motivated by financial or non-financial benefits and determine whether sustainable business practices impact financial performance.

3.4. Research Model

This subsection presents the models tested in the study and the proxy variables used to measure entrepreneurial intention, sustainable business practices, and financial performance.

Entrepreneurial intentions impact sustainability by influencing entrepreneurs' decisions towards sustainable business practices. Intentions shape the willingness to pursue environmentally and socially conscious business practices, whether or not the intentions result in monetary or nonfinancial gains. Despite intentions being abstract concepts that cannot be measured directly, proxy variables can be used to quantify them. For instance, the adoption rate of eco-friendly technology, integration of sustainable practices, and commitment to social responsibility are some of the proxies that can be used to measure these variables. Luckily for this study, ESG scores for companies exist that can be used to quantify entrepreneurial intentions toward sustainability. ESG scores are metrics that gauge a firm's commitment to sustainable practices. The environmental factors in the ESG metric look into a company's practices on the planet, including emissions and resource utilisation, whereas governance focuses on adherence to ethical principles and leadership. The social aspect of ESG metrics gauges corporations' association with the community, investors, and stakeholders. Based on the insight, the ESG metrics provide comprehensive measure factors all impacting sustainability.

In this study, computing ESG for studied companies will not be necessary as many ESG rating agencies do the work independently on behalf of investors. Among the companies doing so include but are not limited to MSCI (formerly Morgan Stanley Capital International), Sustainalytics, ISS ESG (Institutional Shareholder Services), FTSE Russell, Vigeo Eiris, Thomson Reuters Eikon ESG Scores, and Dow Jones Sustainability Indices (DJSI). While these companies all contribute to measuring the ESG scores of various companies, their computed ESG scores face several limitations. First, the companies lack standardisation in measuring ESG scores of companies. Rating agencies apply varied methodologies when measuring ESG scores, implying that different

agencies might have different ESG scores in different rating agencies. As a result, comparing ESG scores across agencies becomes a challenging task.

Besides, ESG computation reliability and validity face data accuracy limitations as its computation by agencies depends on company disclosers that may not be comprehensive and accurate. Greenwashing or limited disclosures can adversely impact the accuracy of ESG score data. Companies reporting sustainable practices might not necessarily mean taking measures towards sustainability. Instead, such reporting may present a false positive impression of ESG factors, resulting in a high score without actual measures towards sustainability. Greenwashing was evident, including in Kim and Yoon (2020), where it was ascertained that companies became the UN's PRI signatories to get investment from environmentally conscious investors without doing anything practical towards enhancing sustainability. Another set of challenges facing the accuracy of ESG scores is variability in quantifying it across industries. Many sectors have different ESG challenges. Hence, one approach is not enough to capture sector-specific scores. Despite sustainability being a long-term force, ESG, on the other hand, is short-term focused and often does not capture the long-term impacts of a corporation's initiatives. As a result, a company could have a high ESG score for investing in short-term initiatives. In contrast, a company investing in long-term sustainability initiatives could have a low ESG score.

The following paragraphs provide insight into the proxies used in this study to evaluate the performance of firms based on their ESG scores.

A company's financial performance is quantified using many metrics, including profitability, liquidity, efficiency, solvency, and market ratios. For this task, interest is kept on profitability ratios, particularly ROA and ROE. ROA quantifies a firm's ability to profit from its assets, whereas ROE measures its ability to generate returns using shareholders' equity. Based on the insight, ROA measures how effectively company assets are used to generate profits. Despite both metrics being essential in determining an enterprise's financial performance, some considerations should be considered. ROE and ROA benchmarks vary across industries. For instance, it is often evident that capital-intensive operations, despite often having high ROE stemming from leverage, often exhibit low

ROA. Besides, debt impacts ROE, considering most companies with high debts often return high ROE despite higher financial risks. Based on the insight, ESG alone is not the only factor impacting these chosen financial performance metrics, adding more complexity to the study.

The following two models are developed for predicting financial performance based on entrepreneurial intentions and sustainability. The liquidity ratio, particularly debt to equity, is added to determine if it impacts ROA and ROE.

$$\text{ROA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{ESG score} + \beta_2 * \text{Debt-to-Assets} \dots \text{model 1}$$

$$\text{ROE} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{ESG score} + \beta_2 * \text{Debt-to-Assets} \dots \text{model 2}$$

3.5. Data Sources and Data Collection

This subsection presents the description of the data sources, their relevance, and how they complement each other, ensuring comprehensive findings on the study topic.

Secondary data was used over primary data because it allows large-scale analysis and historical comparisons, is cost-efficient, and reduces risks involved in the research. Only credible sources were used in the data collection process. Government databases, industry reports, academic research, ESG rating agencies, WSJ, WRDS, and archives of international organisations were considered when retrieving relevant data for the study. These official sources present a general overview of the entrepreneurial landscape with statistics on business registration, industry trends, and economic indicators. They expose the macro forces defining the Kingdom's economic landscape, a critical background for understanding entrepreneurs. Next, this study embarks on the journey into the green thickets of industry reports. Other specialised reports, written by experienced analysts and market researchers, provided in-depth information on particular areas, including rising trends such as sustainability. They provided individual challenges and opportunities for green entrepreneurs.

A wealth of knowledge on entrepreneurial intention, sustainability practices, and corporations was gathered among peer-reviewed studies and scholarly journals. These rigorous inquiries provided helpful theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence; they became the foundation for the analysis. Finally, international organisations' databases were searched, including institutions such as the World Bank and the United Nations, which have vast data on economic development, sustainability, and entrepreneurial ecosystems all around the globe. International organisations' datasets provided essential baselines for comparing KSA's progress to other countries, offering insight into the Kingdom's singular position among nations in sustainable entrepreneurship.

The companies whose data were analysed in the quantitative part of the study were 17: KSA Oil Co, Abdullah Al Othaim Markets Co, Advanced Petrochemical Co, Al Dawaa Medical Services Co, Al Rajhi Bank, Almarai Co, Arabian Cement Co, Middle East Healthcare Co, Najran Cement Co, Riyadh Bank, KSA Mining Co, KSA Refineries Co, Al-Jouf Agricultural Development Co, Saudi Electricity Co, Saudi Awwal Bank, Mobile Telecommunications Co. KSA, and Elm Co. (KSA). These companies operate in different sectors: Oil and gas Products/Services, Food Retail, Chemicals, Drug Retail, Banking, Food Products, Building Materials/Products, Healthcare Provision, Mining, Refiners/pipelines, Utilities, Telecommunication, and Software and services. Having companies from different sectors was important for generalising the study findings.

A systematic literature review was necessary because the quantitative analysis had to pass through the triangulation process for rigorous assessments of consistency, validity, and quality standards, creating the foundation of its integrity. While these datasets provide a wealth of information, they shed light on all the subtle aspects characterising human experience. As a result, reviewing already conducted qualitative research was necessary to reveal the results obtained from the data analysis.

The study of sustainability and entrepreneurial intentions in KSA involves various data sets. The datasets include governmental databases, industry reports, academic research databases, international organisation data, environmental impact assessments, social responsibility reports, financial performance indicators, and innovation indices.

I. Government Databases

Government databases can provide information on regulatory frameworks, requirements for business registration, KSA's economic indicators, and government initiatives that support entrepreneurial activities.

II. Industry Reports

Industry reports can provide datasets on market growth, emerging trends, and sustainability benchmarks in different sectors, which eventually help develop contextual dynamics. For instance, reports on sector industries usually provide information on sustainability measures and entrepreneurship.

III. Academic Research Databases

Academic research databases provide comprehensive scholarly perspectives on sustainability and entrepreneurial intentions. One can access information on empirical data, theoretical models, and shreds of evidence from peer-reviewed sources.

IV. International Organizations' Data

International organisations like the International Monetary Fund and World Bank incorporate global perspectives. Using such organisations provides datasets that provide a broader picture of entrepreneurship that can be compared to cross-country data.

V. Environmental Impact Assessments

Developing a sustainable business requires an understanding of environmental impacts. Environmental impact assessments provide evaluations incorporating recycling practices, energy use, and waste disposal strategies relevant to building sustainability in business.

VI. Social Responsibility Reports

Reports on social responsibility incorporate databases that illustrate how a business influences society. The reports include information on community engagement, the ethical practices of a business, and philanthropic activities that support social sustainability.

VII. Financial Performance Indicators

The financial performance of a sustainable business can be evaluated through market share, revenue, and profit margin metrics. Through financial reports, one can access datasets with such financial metrics.

VIII. Innovation Indices

In an entrepreneurial ecosystem, datasets that include innovation indices can be obtained from innovation dynamics like patent applications, research and development projects, and emerging technological advancements. Such datasets support creativity in entrepreneurial initiatives.

3.6. Variables and Data Analysis

Four variables were collected in this study: ESG score, ROA, ROE, and Debt-to-Assets ratio. These variables are used to determine Entrepreneurial intentions and sustainable business practices' impacts on financial performance. ROA and ROE are the dependent variables in the two proposed regression models, 1 and 2. On the other hand, Debt-to-Assets and ESG scores are the independent variables. The set of analyses proposed in this study is broadly divided into quantitative analysis and systematic literature review, which the following subsections discuss in detail.

3.6.1. Quantitative Analysis

Descriptive and inferential analyses were conducted to provide insights into the collected data's distribution, dispersion, and measures of central tendency and to draw conclusions. Considering entrepreneurial intention towards sustainability was abstract, ESG scores were used to quantify it, and ESG scores are continuous numeric scores suitable for quantitative analysis. Besides, the ratings are arranged in an inherently ordered manner, making them suitable for descriptive statistics. With measures of central tendency and distributions drawing insights into KSA's entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainability, they will be evident together with the direction of their respective inclinations. Following descriptive statistics was an inferential analysis to determine the association between the study variables, particularly the impact of sustainable business practices on financial performance. Considering the modelled regression models (models 1 and 2) have more than one regressor, multivariate regression analysis was the most appropriate test for each of the regression models—the study's main aim was to investigate the association between ESG score and financial performance. However, the Debt-to-Assets ratio was added to provide insights into whether debt, too, was a factor impacting financial performance as debt affects company sustainability.

Some assumptions must be met for the regression model to be valid and reliable, and the developed model (models 1 and 2) is no different. Linearity is the first assumption that had to be met. When performing linear multivariate regression analysis, the independent variables are assumed to have a linear association with the dependent variable. That is, ESG score and Debt-to-Assets must have a linear relationship with ROE and ROA. The second assumption is the independence of errors. This assumption holds that residuals should be independent of each other. This implies that the values of errors that the ESG score presents should not predict the values of errors that the Debt-to-Assets ratio predicts. The third assumption is homoscedasticity, which requires that the variance of errors in the independent variables, ESG score, and Debt-to-Assets ratio be constant across all levels. The final assumptions were normality, requiring residuals to be normally

distributed, and multicollinearity, necessitating the absence of a perfect linear association among ESG and Debt-to-Assets ratio. With these assumptions met, the following regression models were run in SPSS.

$$\text{ROA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{ESG score} + \beta_2 * \text{Debt-to-Assets} \dots \text{model 1}$$

$$\text{ROE} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{ESG score} + \beta_2 * \text{Debt-to-Assets} \dots \text{model 2}$$

3.6.2. Systematic Literature Review Analysis

This subsection provides insights into the steps followed when conducting the systematic literature review to safeguard its acceptance by systematic review platforms like PROSPERO.

This analysis was conducted following PROSPERO CRD42024495871 guidelines funded by the NIHR and produced by CRD (PROSPERO, n.d.). PROSPERO denotes an international database with prospective registered systematic literature reviews. Based on this insight, PROSPERO aims to provide a hub of comprehensive studies registered at commencement to prevent duplication and biased reporting. This is accomplished by comparing the submitted review with what is planned in PROSPERO's portal (PROSPERO, n.d.). As a result, the publications in this study using PROSPERO as a data source are cited to prevent duplication. Before registering for a systematic review with PROSPERO, the researcher ensured that PROSPERO's standards for eligibility were met and that the submitted review integrated all the methodological details.

Besides, the researcher followed PRISMA guidelines when conducting the systematic literature review. PRISMA denotes an evidence-based minimum set of items to meet when conducting meta-analyses or systematic reviews. With PRISMA, it was possible to report the systematic review transparently (PRISMA, n.d.). While many PRISMA guidelines are rarely updated, this study settled for the latest PRISMA statement 2020,

which replaced the 2009 guidelines, when determining the minimum set of items for systematic review. PRISMA flow diagram presented in Figure 1 came in handy when depicting information flow through various phases of the literature review. The diagram mapped out the number of studies identified, excluded, and included, with information regarding their exclusion. More details on the PRISMA diagram are reported following the search strategy description in the forthcoming paragraphs. It is worth noting that the synthesis review was conducted by the PRISMA 2020 expanded checklist (PRISMA, n.d.).

Following PROSPERO's guidelines for systematic review, the following steps were followed to ensure the review was comprehensive and relevant to the study topic (PRISMA, n.d.). The first step was listing any possible conflict of interest that could impact the study outcome, such as personal beliefs that could impact scientific judgment. Once this was done, the research questions and objectives were reviewed, ensuring broad questions were broken into specific questions, as evident in the study. When breaking down the main research question, resulting in two questions, this was done with PI(E)COS question framing to ensure the research questions had a purpose, information, broader context, constraints, operations, and stakeholders in mind. The developed research questions framed the literature searches.

All the systematically reviewed literature was obtained by searching credible and scholarly databases, namely EBSCOhost (Business Source Complete), ProQuest (ABI/INFORM Collection), ScienceDirect, JSTOR (Journal Storage), PubMed, Emerald Insight, IEEE Xplore, Scopus, Web of Science, SpringerLink, Wiley Online Library, Google Scholar, Taylor & Francis Online, SSRN (Social Science Research Network), SAGE Journals, Nature Sustainability, Harvard Business Review (HBR), Financial Times (FT.com), The Journal of Sustainable Finance & Banking, Journal of Business Ethics, International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology, ABI/INFORM Collection, Business Source Complete, ABI/INFORM Global, Sustainability Science, and Business Ethics Quarterly. Only studies and articles within ten years were reviewed to ensure the review was up-to-date.

The search strategy adopted only terms related to entrepreneurial intentions, sustainability, and financial performance. These terms were combined with keywords relevant to the study topic, ensuring search results returned relevant sources. When searching for articles, all studies relevant to the study topic were selected, provided their context was about entrepreneurial intention association with sustainability and sustainable business practices' effect on financial performance. Despite the study mainly focusing on KSA, search results of studies conducted in KSA were prioritised. However, studies from different nations on the topic were considered to provide context to this study's findings. PROSPERO's guidelines necessitate providing the expected primary outcome of a review, including measures and measurements, which resulted in the researcher developing a chapter set aside expressly for the expected outcome. (Chapter 5). The following subsection presents data extraction and quality assessment when conducting the systematic review.

Figure 1 shows the PRISMA flow diagram presenting information flow in various stages of the systematic review, mapping out the number of records identified, excluded, included, and reasons for exclusion and inclusion. While many PRISMA flow diagram templates exist on the PRISMA website, a more comprehensive one comprising database searches, registers, and other sources was adopted. Below is the developed PRISMA flow diagram of this study's systematic review.

Figure 1: PRISMA flow diagram highlighting source identification, screening, inclusion, and exclusion.

3.6.2.1. Data Extraction and Quality Assessment

In total, 41 pieces of literature were reviewed, with the primary information extracted being ESG scores, its limitations, Entrepreneurs' intention to invest in ESG, CSR, CSR impact on financial performance, determinants of entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainability, factors affecting entrepreneurs' intentions to adopt ESG, the impact of ESG scores on ROE and ROA. The data extracted was mainly in the context of KSA. Purposive sampling was used when extracting data from the sources, implying that any relevant source with needed information was considered. Nevertheless, the data extraction was blinded, considering the researcher was unaware of the journals or articles selected before data extraction. No manipulation of the collected data was necessary as the collected information aimed to triangulate the findings of the quantitative part of this study.

Once the information was collected, it was interpreted to the best of the researcher's knowledge and paraphrased and cited in the study findings as explanations or a significant finding. The internal validity of the reviewed studies was assessed through triangulation with other studies to determine the points of convergence and divergence in the resented results and explanations.

3.6.2.2. Data Synthesis Strategy

Quantitative and narrative data synthesis approaches were adopted to synthesise the collected information. Planned analytical approaches were adopted, aiding in categorising studies within their respective narrative synthesis. A limited scope of meta-analysis was expected, considering only a limited range of outcomes was anticipated.

3.7. Validity and Reliability

This subsection provides insights into approaches put in place to ensure the reliability and validity of the study and how they were quantified.

Validity and reliability determine how well an adopted methodology measures the outcome or the dependent variable. Validity denotes the accuracy of a measure adopted, whereas reliability deals with the reproducibility of the findings, implying internal consistency. This study was completed following a mixed research strategy involving quantitative and systematic literature review. As stated earlier, the systematic review aimed to triangulate the findings from the quantitative analysis, thereby improving the study findings' validity. Talking about validity, several approaches were put in place to ensure the phenomenon under investigation returns accurate results. To ensure construct validity, the study variables were clearly defined to ensure that the researcher

measured only what was intended to measure, in this case, entrepreneurs' intention towards sustainability using ESG scores and financial performance using ROA, ROE, and Debt-to-Assets ratio.

To ensure construct validity, the researcher ensured that ESG scores, ROA, ROE, and Debt-to-Assets ratio measures captured all construct aspects, ensuring completeness and relevance. While criterion-related validity that involves comparing measurement instruments with other measures was not undertaken, triangulation was used to ensure that the findings were consistent with measures used in other systematically reviewed literature. Internal validity was guaranteed in the study by ensuring that the adopted study design minimised the occurrence of possible explanations for the quantified associations. On the other hand, external validity was safeguarded by analysing entrepreneurs or companies operating in different sectors of the economy within different periods, improving the generalizability of the study.

On the other hand, the reliability of the adopted systematic literature review was safeguarded by following PRISMA and PROSPERO guidelines. This was achieved by defining inclusion and exclusion criteria, adopting a relevant search strategy based on relevant keywords, adopting a systematic data extraction process, and conducting a quality assessment of the selected studies before review. Besides, triangulation of the selected sources was done among each other, determining points of convergence and divergence, thereby improving the review reliability. Most importantly, only credible and scholarly sources were used when reviewing the 41 selected sources. Transparent reporting was vital in this study, enhancing its reproducibility and reliability. PRISMA guidelines and registering the review with PROSPERO enabled transparency and prevented duplication of reviews.

4. Ethical Consideration

This section outlines the credibility and integrity of the research process followed, ensuring that the data and information that form the cornerstone of this study protect the rights of the data source owners.

A secondary study resulted in the ethical consideration not revolving around study participants. As a result, factors such as anonymity and confidentiality were not crucial to the study. Nevertheless, measures were taken to protect the data owners' rights. Only publicly available data regarding organisation data from the research companies was utilised. Information and data that were readily available online were collected, and credit was given to the owners by citing their works and data sources. Data use agreements were followed when using secondary data. In particular, when analysing company data, the information provided to investors that allows for analysis of the financial performance and sustainability measures such as ESG scores were used without de-identifying the companies nor anonymising them as the data provided by publicly listed companies and ESG rating companies are for public use. However, the intellectual property rights of the data sources were respected, including complying with data sharing or restrictions rules.

Publication bias was avoided by ensuring the study remained objective, eliminating biased representations of available evidence. Besides, fair use and copyright were adhered to when using extant literature data and findings. Having followed PRISMA and PROSPERO's guidelines, transparent reporting was vital, with clearly defined and elaborated methods used for secondary analysis, enhancing reproducibility and replicability of the research. Besides, plagiarism was avoided by ensuring that any information from outside sources used in the study was cited and credit given to the author. While the study was conducted objectively, it was essential to take note of personal biases and preconceptions. To ensure this did not impact the study, following PROSPERO's guidelines, conflicts of interest were first identified before selecting systematic literature to review. Acknowledging the possible conflict of interest provides readers with a better understating of some researcher bias that would have impacted the

study findings, thereby acting as a disclaimer. Having provided the ethical considerations adopted when completing the, it was also deemed ethical to point out some of the study's limitations that could have impacted the study findings.

5. Expected Outcome

This chapter focuses mainly on the quantitative part of the study, considering it covers predicting the association between entrepreneurial intention and sustainable business practices. Besides, the expected contributions of the study are presented. Extant literature findings are utilised to make predictions of the anticipated results. Detailed information on the expected outcomes are presented in the following paragraphs.

Regarding the association between sustainable business practices' impact on financial performance, as evident from the findings from the literature review, the relationship between the two variables can be insignificant, significant with positive associations, or significant with negative associations. While different findings were anticipated in the study based on the past study findings, it is undisputed that sustainable business practices have non-financial benefits to society. Nevertheless, mixed findings were anticipated regarding entrepreneurial intentions and motives towards sustainability, informing policymakers of some of the complex associations and multifaced nature of business intentions and sustainability.

The study summarises and integrates a wide range of literature that offers an overall understanding of the factors shaping entrepreneurial intentions from the sustainability perspective. The study presents an intricate perspective on what influences entrepreneurial motivations by critically analysing personal values, environmental attitudes, healing psyche, social norms, and perceived feasibility. This contribution contributes to existing knowledge by adding granularity, as it offers a detailed map of the psychological and social topography that shapes sustainable entrepreneurial intentions. If one understands that powerful intentions will lead to genuinely productive entrepreneurial action, it becomes easier to forecast how an entrepreneur will likely act. This predictive insight qualifies theoretical models and has a practical meaning for policymakers, business development services, and educators as they aim to develop sustainable entrepreneurship.

The study focuses on the early phase of the entrepreneurial process, particularly intentions. It offers a unique view into cognitive processes preceding actual entrepreneurial actions. By delving into the intentions stage, the research contributes to knowledge regarding how entrepreneurs traverse decision-making and cognitive pathways leading up to venturing. This early-stage understanding adds a critical dimension to the time dynamics of entrepreneurship studies. This research connects theory with practice by presenting concrete policy proposals and putting the educational value of understanding entrepreneurial intentions into focus. The insights help policymakers design interventions to support sustainable ventures. At the same time, teachers can use these principles as a part of curricula and thus prepare future generations for entrepreneurial activities with more practical knowledge about sustainability. Thus, the study acts as a connector between scholarly knowledge and real-world practice.

Although focused on KSA, the results of this study have a cross-cultural significance. The identified determinants and their effects on entrepreneurial intentions inform a deeper comprehension of the elements that are both culturally and universally relevant. Consequently, this cross-cultural relevancy allows for transferability; insights from the KSA context can inform discussions and strategies in multitudinous global entrepreneurial networks. The study uses a systematic literature review method, following PRISMA and PROSPERO guidelines to ensure its methodological rigour in socio-economic studies on entrepreneurship. The transparent and reproducible nature of the meticulous protocol development-systematic literature search and criteria-based selection process ensures complete transparency. This methodological contribution increases the reliability and validity of findings in this study, acting as a benchmark for future research projects. The study forms part of the growing debate on responsible research practices due to its focus on ethical considerations and integrity in dealing with data. Data privacy, data use agreements, and the integrity of secondary data analysis are discussed explicitly to set a benchmark for ethical practice in entrepreneurship research. This plays into the more significant trend toward research transparency and integrity.

6. Results and Discussion

In this chapter this study explores the research results, in detail drawing insights from a review of existing literature to shed light on the connection between entrepreneurial aspirations and the integrations of sustainable business practices. The analysis carefully examines how these findings relate to business operations and policy formulation.

To begin with this section takes a dive into the SPSS analysis of data to identify key factors that influence sustainability. It aims to uncover whether sustainable business practices have an impact on performance. Additionally, the systematic literature review acts as a framework combining research findings and placing them within the context of existing discussions. This thorough analysis examines variables such as ESG scores, risk assessments, exposure levels, management approaches, debt to assets ratio, ROA and ROE starting with statistics and moving towards more advanced analyses.

The research delves in the results it is important to revisit the research questions that guided this investigation. This reflection ensures a connection between the data collected and the theoretical inquiries posed at the beginning of this research endeavor. It highlights the relevance of these questions in shaping the narrative towards an understanding of how entrepreneurial goals intersect with sustainability in a business setting.

Continuing from the research questions the discussion progresses on a manner examining the significance of the results in comparison, the existing literature. This section not uncovers. Differences from past studies but also considers how these insights can influence business strategy development and policy making. Looking through this perspective the conversation explores ways to incorporate practices into entrepreneurial activities emphasizing the crucial role of ESG factors.

6.1. Descriptive Analysis Results

The nominal data among the studied companies were management, ESG rating, and exposure to sustainability risks.

Beginning with management, it was evident that KSA companies cutting across different sectors did not score high on management based on Sustainalytics ratings. Instead, 52.9 and 47.1 scored average and weak ratings in management, as evident in Table 1.

Table 1: Management rating of companies in KSA

		Management			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Average	9	52.9	52.9	52.9
	Weak	8	47.1	47.1	100.0
	Total	17	100.0	100.0	

Expounding on the management findings, these results affect managing ESG risks. This subpar management recorded by KSA companies likely implies a systemic deficiency in the studied corporations' ability to mitigate and efficiently address ESG risks. It is worth noting that management, as does sustainability, plays a pivotal role when making ESG considerations. The weak management rating exhibited by 47.1% of the studied companies suggests potential vulnerabilities in internal controls, strategic planning, and stakeholder engagement, all important to sustainability. With such a low management rating, many KSA corporations studied are expected to experience heightened exposure to ESG risks or have high unmanned ESG-related risks. Given the insights presented, management forms one of the determinants of entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainability in a broader context with specific context involving factors such as perception of risk, knowledge, and organisational culture, to name a few.

These management results imply its multifaced impacts on sustainability and entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainability. To begin with, inadequate strategic

planning may lead to oversight of emerging ESG and sustainability risks, resulting in the absence of intentions or leaving corporations ill-prepared to manage them by societal expectations. Second, weak stakeholder engagement results in inadequate constructive associations with investors, customers, and the community, failing to comprehend stakeholders' concerns and heightening social risks. Finally, the absence of internal controls exacerbates governance and environmental risks, resulting in poor oversight and reporting, contributing to compliance violations, environmental degradation, and unsustainable and unethical business practices. Based on the insight, there exist gaps in KSA companies' management, which likely results in undesirable intentions towards sustainable business practices.

The weak management rating of 47.1% observed in the results, which is caused poor cooperative management in internal controls, strategic planning, and stakeholders engagement, has been identified by some authors (Cronan, 2022; Eliwa et al., 2021; Reber et al., 2022) who in their study noted that poor cooperate management in internal controls, strategic planning, and stakeholders engagement threatens the survival of newly established firms and can have a significant negative impact on profitability and stock prices. Chen et al., 2021 contribute to these study findings, noting that using ESG may improve risk and opportunity management, which benefits consumers, workers, supply chain participants, and management. Similarly, Gregory et al. (2021) noted that poor stakeholder engagement in a company results in a lack of understanding when addressing stakeholder concerns in general organisation meetings. As a result, it increases ESG social risks in the company. Furthermore, (Maignan et al., 2021; Ramady & Saeed, 2021) add to the findings that poor management of internal controls in the company results in governance and environmental risks that could lead the company to compliance violations and unsustainable business practices.

Moving forward to exposure to ESG risk, KSA companies generally exhibit medium exposure to ESG risks, accounting for 58.8% of the companies across different sectors of the economy. The medium exposure to ESG risk is seconded, with high exposure accounting for 29.4%, whereas companies least exposed to ESG risk account for 11.8%.

Table 2 provides insight into ESG risk rating by percentage for different corporations in KSA.

Table 2: Exposure to ESG risk breakdown for KSA companies

		Exposure			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	High	5	29.4	29.4	29.4
	Low	2	11.8	11.8	41.2
	Medium	10	58.8	58.8	100.0
	Total	17	100.0	100.0	

The exposure to ESG risk in KSA companies implies a need for heightening attention and intentions towards proactive management, which plays a pivotal role in managing ESG factors across various sectors. The inclination towards high exposure to ESG risks implies elevated susceptibility to operation, reputation, and financial risks from insufficient management of governance structures, environmental impacts, and social and cultural factors. Companies in KSA exhibiting high exposure to ESG risk will likely face stakeholders' disapproval, operation disruptions, and regulatory scrutiny. Most companies experiencing high exposure to ESG risks fell in the category of Oil and gas Products/Services, Utilities, Mining, Chemicals and Food Products. The 11.8% of the corporations exhibiting low exposure to ESG risks in this study were regarded as leaders in sustainable business practices. Specifically, some of these companies were health organisations like Al Dawaa Medical Services Co. and Middle East Healthcare Co. Looking at the categories with high and low exposure to ESG risks, they exhibit different intentions towards sustainability, with the health sector widely focusing on sustainability. The implication of the exposure to ESG risk has profound impacts on sustainability in KSA. The descriptive results for this variable underscore a dire need for a systematic shift towards sustainable business practices to reduce unmanaged ESG risks.

Several pieces of literature from authors like (Karwowski et al., 2021 Nirino et al., 2021 Rakipi & D'Onza,2023) support the study findings. According to their studies, the authors indicated that companies with high exposure to ESG risks are prone to several

operational, reputational, and financial risks. As a result, Kibsey et al. (2021) emphasize that companies must proactively manage ESG factors proactively. Additionally, studies by (Amuah, 2023; Liu, 2019; and Ziolo, 2021) contribute to the study findings by clarifying that the overall ESG score in a company is affected chiefly directly or indirectly by insufficient management of governance structures. This aligns with the observation that companies in sectors such as Oil and gas, Utilities, Mining, Chemicals, and Food Products are likely to face stakeholders' disapproval, operation disruptions, and regulatory scrutiny. The findings from (Nirino et al., 2021; and Rakipi & D'Onza, 2023) also support the study findings, indicating there is a need for KSA companies to shift towards sustainable business practices that promote long-term sustainability in order to reduce unmanaged ESG risks, which is caused due to poor proactive management of ESG factors in a company.

The following section covers ESG risk ratings for KSA's corporations. Sustainalytics ranked this variable using four categories ranging from low to severe. As evident in Table 3, the majority of the KSA corporations studied, 41.2%, exhibit a medium ESG risk rating, seconded by a severe rating accounting for 29.4%. A high ESG risk rating comes third with 23.5%, whereas only 5.9% of KSA's corporations studied exhibit a low ESG risk rating. These findings show that while most KSA corporations exhibit a medium ESG risk rating, the skewness tends to extend towards a severe ESG risk rating.

Table 3: ESG risk rating for KSA companies

		ESG Risk Rating			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	High	4	23.5	23.5	23.5
	Low	1	5.9	5.9	29.4
	Medium	7	41.2	41.2	70.6
	Severe	5	29.4	29.4	100.0
	Total	17	100.0	100.0	

ESG risk ratings for the studies of KSA corporations show that KSA companies are grappling with challenges stemming from unsustainable business practices. The

variable's descriptive statistics being skewed towards severe depict a heightened level towards exposure to ESG and sustainability risks. Besides, this shows weak management resulting in far-reaching consequences, including but not limited to operational disruptions, regulatory penalties, stakeholders' disapproval, and reputational damage. The minority, in this case, comprises companies accounting for 5.9%. These companies exemplify sustainable business practices and operate in health sectors, whereas corporations failing to meet sustainable business practices operate in the Chemicals, Mining, Refiners/Pipeline, Building Materials/Products, Utilities, Oil & Gas Products/ Services, and Food Products sectors.

The study findings indicate a skewed distribution towards severe risk ratings and expose unsustainable business practices among corporations in KSA. This aligns with findings from (Li & Wu, 2020 Antoncic, 2019 Lipton et al., 2021), suggesting that weak ESG management leads to significant consequences such as operational disruptions and reputational damage. The minority of corporations with low ESG risk ratings that exemplify sustainable practices in the health sector (Yang & Han, 2023) note that these companies prioritise social responsibility, transparency, and innovation, contributing to societal well-being and long-term environmental sustainability. Conversely, Torpey (2020) contributes to the study findings that sectors like chemicals, mining, and utilities demonstrate higher ESG risks due to their significant environmental impact, such as pollution, habitat destruction, and resource depletion. Hazen (2020) adds that higher ESG risks in these sectors lead to heightened scrutiny and regulatory oversight regarding their ESG performance. Hazen (2020) adds that corporations in this sector can implement comprehensive sustainability strategies to address ESG concerns and mitigate associated risks.

Moving forward to continuous and numerical variables, summary statistics analysed included measures of central tendencies, dispersion, and distribution. Table 4 shows the computed descriptive statistics of ESG scores, Debt-to-Assets, ROE, and ROA of KSA's companies studied.

Table 4: ESG scores, Debt-to-Assets, ROA, and ROE descriptive statistics

Descriptive Statistics

	N Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness Statistic	Std. Error
ESG Score	17	19.5	50.3	34.171	9.3103	.492	.550
Debt-To-Assets%	17	2.21	58.54	25.3106	15.77959	.727	.550
ROA%	17	.93	25.66	6.8965	7.16830	1.691	.550
ROE%	17	2.60	77.80	18.3365	19.59619	2.053	.550
Valid N (listwise)	17						

The following paragraphs discuss the descriptive analyses of the variables ESG scores, Debt-to-Assets, ROE, and ROA and their implications.

Beginning with ESG scores, on average, KSA's corporations scored 34.17 with a standard deviation of 9.31, implying medium variability or dispersion. ESG ratings had a positive skewness of 0.49, implying that many KSA corporations tend to record lower ESG scores than the mean. These findings reflect the ESG risk rating and exposure to ESG risks, suggesting that, on average, the studied KSA companies have medium to high unmanaged ESG risks. The ESG score findings have a significant on KSA's overall sustainability landscape, indicating the need for a systemic shift to proactive management.

Hübel & Scholz (2020) suggest that a positive skewness in ESG scores in a company indicates potential challenges or deficiencies in their environmental, social, and governance practices. This aligns with our study findings; ESG scores among KSA corporations had medium variability with a tendency towards lower scores, indicating exposure to ESG risks. These findings echo research by Izcan and Bektas (2022), indicating that companies should adopt regulatory frameworks and incentives to prioritise sustainability and achieve higher ESG scores. Dunn et al. (2022) note that Collaborative efforts between government, businesses, civil society, and investors are essential to drive meaningful change and foster a culture of sustainability in KSA.

Moving to the Debt-to-Assets ratio, KSA companies recorded a mean value of 25.31% with positive skewness, implying that most KSA corporations tend to record a lower debt-to-assets ratio than the mean. The average debt ratio has both positive and negative

implications for sustainable business practices. Despite exhibiting high variability, the overall average debt ratio is low, implying a conservative financial approach in KSA towards debt, contributing to corporations' financial sustainability. That stated, overall, KSA's corporations studied are generally positioned to weather market uncertainties and economic downturns, implying that with regard to financial sustainability, the entrepreneur's lending intentions foster long-term sustainability. The conservative approach to lending minimises financial risks. While this is good, it can limit companies from acquiring debt for strategic investment into sustainable business practices. This is because strategic investments into sustainable business practices necessitate upfront investing and a more balanced debt-to-equity structure, often achieved by leveraging debt.

The majority of the KSA corporations recorded lower ratios than the mean. This highlights a conservative financial approach towards debt, contributing to corporations' financial sustainability. D'Orazio (2023) supports this observation by emphasising that the conservative approach to maintaining a lower Debt-to-Assets ratio can affect sustainability by limiting investments in sustainable practices. However, Parrot & Tierney (2022) suggest that a balanced debt-to-equity structure is required from the companies experiencing lower ratios than mean to make strategic investments in environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices. Grabinska et al. contribute to the study findings by emphasising a lower debt-to-assets ratio than the mean, indicating a conservative approach which can limit companies from making strategic investments in sustainable practices. Dunn et al. (2022) suggest that leveraging debt for strategic investments in sustainability can yield long-term benefits.

The average ROE among the studied KSA companies was 18.34%, with a high skewness of 2.05, implying a long right tail confirming the presence of outliers. This is evident considering the minimum ROE is 2.60%, whereas the maximum ROE is 77.80%, giving a significant range. With the skewness of 2.05, it is evident that most of the ROEs of KSA corporations studied tend to fall below the mean value of 18.34%. Finally, ROA descriptive statistics depict a mean of 6.9% with a high positive skewness of 1.69, suggesting that most ROA of the studied KSA companies tend to fall below the mean

value of 6.9%. This is evident from the descriptive statistics, with the company with the least and the highest ROA recoding 0.93% and 25.66%, respectively. Sustainable business practices necessitate profitability and financial sustainability. While the average high ROE is promising, the skewness and high standard deviation imply that many of the studied corporations face difficulties in ensuring consistent ROEs, raising concern about the sustainability of their returns. Corporations with high ROA and ROE can invest in sustainable business practices upfront, whereas those with low ROE and ROA need a robust shift to proactive strategic management.

The average ROE among the studied KSA companies was 18.34% with a high skewness of 2.05, implying a long right tail confirming the presence of outliers highlights significant variability in profitability and financial performance. (Finta et al., 2022; Mohammed, S. 2022) supports these observations by emphasising that variability in profitability can impact sustainability by influencing companies' ability to consistently generate returns necessary for long-term investments in sustainable practices. Similarly, Lasana (2022) notes that the average high ROE in a company can be promising, but the presence of outliers and the high skewness suggest challenges in maintaining consistent returns. Additionally, Izcan and Bektas (2022) align with the study findings, noting that companies with a higher positive skewness of ROA may struggle to achieve returns above the mean value. As a result, they need to achieve company sustainability goals and practical efforts to address ESG concerns.

6.2. Inferential Statistics Analysis Results

Unlike the descriptive statistics section, this section concludes by determining causation based on regression analysis results. While the main focus was determining whether sustainable business practices affect financial performance and the direction of the associations, a regression model was run to determine how management impacted

sustainability, providing insight into whether management determines sustainability. In this case, sustainability was measured using an unmanaged ESG risk rating variable.

A multinomial logistic regression model was run, considering the ESG risk rating variable had four levels. ESG rating was the dependent variable, whereas management was the factor variable. In this regression model, no covariates were added. The result is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Effect of management on ESG risk Rating

Model Fitting Information				
Model	Model Fitting		Likelihood Ratio Tests	
	Criteria			
	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	13.793			
Final	10.936	2.857	3	.041

As evident from Table 5, with a p-value of 0.041 that is less than the 0.05 alpha, a conclusion is reached that a significant association exists between management and ESG risk rating. This implies that management is a significant determinant of entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainability in KSA among the studied companies.

Following the analysis of the impact of management on sustainable business practices was the effect of sustainable business practices on financial performance. This analysis used a linear regression model, considering a linear association was anticipated between the financial performance and the dependent variables (ESG scores and Debt-to-Interest). The following are the scatter plots depicting the association between the regression variables.

Figure 2: Scatter plot showing the association between ROA and ESG scores

As evident from Figure 2, ROA and ESG scores exhibit a positive linear association with a directly proportional relationship. This implies that among the studied companies, ROA increases with an increase in unmanaged ESG risk in KSA. This implies that the efficiency in generating returns from assets among the studied KSA companies tends to increase with increased unmanaged ESG risks, implying that investing in sustainability does not benefit the studied companies. The descriptive statistical analyses show that most KSA companies exhibit weak management when managing ESG risk. Looking solely at ROA association with ESG scores, it could be inferred that entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainability in KSA do not focus on sustainability to surge ROA.

The association between ESG scores and ROE return conflicting results on the association between unmanaged ESG risks and financial performance.

Figure 3: Scatter plot showing the association between ROE and ESG scores

Figure 3 shows a negative association between ESG scores and ROE, implying that as ESG scores increase, ROE decrease. The inversely proportional association shows that ROE increases with an increase in sustainable business practices as ESG scores denote the percentage of unmanaged ESG risks. In other words, the efficiency in using equity capital to generate profits surges in the studied KSA companies when unmanaged ESG risks decrease.

Overall, the implication of sustainability on ROA and ROE in the studied KSA corporations is multifaced and complex, suggesting varying management approaches towards ESG risks with intentions focusing on financial stability rather than sustainability. Following the scatter plot discussion are the regression modelling (model 1 and 2) and the implication of their outputs.

Tests were conducted first to determine if Debt-to-Assets predicted ROA and ROE before including it as a regressor in models 1 and 2. The regression output returned a p-value of more than 0.05 in both tests, implying that Debt-to-Assets was not a significant predictor

of ROA and ROE of the analysed KSA companies. As a result, the variable was dropped from the analysis, and models 1 and 2 were revised as follows.

$$\text{ROA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{ESG score} \dots \text{model 1}$$

$$\text{ROE} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{ESG score} \dots \text{model 2}$$

Tables 6 and 7 present the regression analysis findings run for models 1 and 2, investigating the effect of sustainable business practices on financial performance.

Table 6: Model 1 regression analysis output

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.169 ^a	.029	-.036	7.29683

a. Predictors: (Constant), ESG Score

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.449	6.925		.354	.729
	ESG Score	.130	.196	.169	.664	.517

a. Dependent Variable: ROA%

As evident from Table 6 results, ESG scores explain only 2.9% of the variability in ROA, with the r-squared value of the model depicting a poor regression line fit. Besides, looking at the coefficients, it is evident that ESG scores have a p-value of 0.517, which is more than the 0.05 alpha. Based on the insight, no significant association exists between sustainable business practices and ROA among the studied KSA companies. As a result, any entrepreneurial intentions towards sustainability in KSA are not geared towards increasing the efficiency of using assets to generate returns.

Table 7: Model 2 regression analysis output

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.148 ^a	.022	-.043	20.01559

a. Predictors: (Constant), ESG Score

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	28.990	18.996		1.526	.148
	ESG Score	-.312	.537	-.148	-.580	.570

a. Dependent Variable: ROE%

Table 7 shows that ESG scores explain only 2.2% of the variability in ROE, and the coefficients table shows an insignificant association between ROE and ESG scores. With the poor regression line fit and the insignificant relationship, a conclusion is reached that there is no association between sustainable business practices and the efficiency of using equity to generate profits among the studied KSA companies.

Overall, a decision was reached that sustainable business practices among the studied KSA companies were not a significant predictor of financial performance.

According to certain research, there is no connection between financial performance and corporate social responsibility. According to McWilliams & Siegel (2021), alternative research reveals positive or negative correlations merely due to issues with the study design, and there is no substantial association between CSR and business performance. When time-series effects are considered, Cho et al. (2020) indicate that no statistically significant association between sustainable business practices and business financial performance is found. According to them, if the study models are more carefully constructed, the favourable link demonstrated in earlier studies will become less pronounced. They contend, therefore, that sustainable business practices cannot improve a company's financial results.

Other studies (Aras et al., 2020 Fauzi et al., K. 2021 Abdelwahed et al., 2021) found no relationship between financial performance and CSR. The study found just a link between firm size and CSR. Galankashi et al., (2021) subsequent study assessed the relationship between sustainable business practices and financial success in two different ways. First, it found that although there is a significant positive correlation between improved financial performance and sustainable business practices, there is no significant association between the two. As a result, Aras et al. (2020) support the claim that there is no relationship between CSR and financial success by pointing out that there may be some causality associated with the times when business size, profitability, risk level, and CSR lag after each other.

Since there is no proof connecting sustainable business practices to financial performance, Jang et al. (2023) claim that there is no problem with R&D intensity not being included as a control variable in their study's first and second hypotheses. Removing R&D intensity would inflate the results if there was a relationship at all, as there is a positive correlation between R&D investment and CSR. Corporate social responsibility and financial performance measures have not been shown to be related, according to Vasilescu et al., (2021). Moreover, it has been found that profitability and R&D intensity do not significantly correlate. According to Sadiq et al., (2020), there is no discernible link between financial success and corporate social responsibility. The authors assert that their research supports a neutral link between CSR and financial performance since larger companies with more resources may be in a better position to invest in CSR initiatives that do not provide immediate financial rewards.

Barbagila et al., (2021) examine the correlation between CSR performance and ROA and the price-earnings ratio using 186 KEJI indices from 2003 to 2009. The study shows no relationship between the price-earnings ratio and ROA and the total of the KEJI indices. Additionally, Omair Alotaibi & Hussainey (2021) add to the findings of Barbagila et al., (2021) by pointing out that their study reclassifies each of the seven evaluation items of the KEJI index into contributions to economic development, contributions to community service, as well as a composite score for examining the relationship with financial results. Contributions to economic development are favorably correlated with ROA and the price-

earnings ratio, according to the results for each index. On the other hand, community service hours do not impact either. Only ROA shows a positive association with the integrated index.

According to Alrib & Flynn, (2022), sustainable business practices initiatives violate shareholder interests because they incur no appreciable additional expenditures beyond the company's initial management actions. They contend that since businesses must grow the economy and create employment, adhering to the original goal of maximizing shareholder profits is fulfilling a social duty in and of itself. Similarly, Soana (2021) examined the connection between British companies' financial performance and corporate social responsibility. The study found no correlation between CSR performance and the price-earnings ratio, which was especially strong in the environmental sector. Financial performance was measured using the price-earnings ratio, and comprehensive performance indicators were used. Three distinct criteria were used to assess CSR performance: community service, employment, and environment. Nirino et al., (2021), looked on the relationship between corporate profitability and CSR. Their reasoning was based on agency theory. According to their argument, managers who overspend on CSR projects in an effort to advance their careers or pursue private utilities drive up agency expenses, which diminish the company's worth.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

The main argument of the study is that despite the KSA supporting entrepreneurial values and factors that strengthen sustainability, attract investments, and build corporate image, KSA companies do not always fully comply with sustainable business practices as a result. One of the tests to assess the validity of the present study was to apply a mixed-method approach by combining different types of analysis: quantitative analysis and systematic literature review. The introduction section of this paper covers the international relevance of ESG investing and its increasing trend globally and locally within the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The adoption of sustainable investment has become quite popular. However, the matter of entrepreneurship and sustainability is more complex in its association between entrepreneurship and sustainability. The statement of problem highlights the KSA's interannual and investors' sustainability, which illustrates the comprehensive views of the various stakeholders on how the initiative will affect cross-border investments. The debates are still on whether KSA's sustainability initiatives could be viewed as a strategy meant only to attract ESG-conscious investors rather than toward factors irrelevant to sustainability. To provide solutions to the issue, this study explores the determinants of entrepreneurial aspirations and their effect on social and financial performance within the KSA. The study's objectives are highlighted, summarising its purpose and looking into it in detail, covering various determinants of sustainable practices and their impacts.

7.1. Quantitative Study Findings

The numbers reported in this study indicate critical insights into the complex connections between the drivers and motives of entrepreneurship, business strategy and sustainability, and the financial outcomes of the companies in the KSA. The results exhibit

that management scores are generally lower across industries, hence raising an alert on possible failings in inner controls, strategic planning, and stakeholders' engagement. These lower scores across the sectors are because businesses without robust management of ESG factors are more exposed to ESG risks. Industries' exposure to ESG risks varies- The medical industry takes the lead in sustainability adoptions, while Oil and gas, Utilities, Mining, Chemicals, and Food Products exhibit comparatively higher exposures. This evidence highlights the urgent need to build up the case for a structured shift from disorderly traditional practices tailored towards exploiting uncontrolled ESG risks to create overall corporate sustainability in KSA.

Moreover, inferential statistical analysis discloses a considerable correlation between management efficiency and ESG risk recognition, thus pointing to management's significant role in orientating entrepreneurs on ESG issues. However, on the other hand, the results obtained' while examining the relationship between sustainable business strategies and financial performance depict a complex and conflicting relationship. Sustainable initiatives correlate weakly with ROA and ROE. However, the study finding suggests that the inducted companies may focus on initiatives that are not beneficial from a financial perspective. Eventually, the study recommends that KSA companies improve their management competencies and implement strategic business policies that can help achieve long-term economic stability in addition to the international expectations of ESG principles.

7.2. Systematic Literature Review Findings

According to the analysis of KSA's entrepreneurial and sustainability landscape, there is an intense interaction between the factors influencing FDIs and the state's adherence to ESG standards. Thanks to the efforts of KSA towards entrepreneurship and attracting FDIs, the sustainability of such ventures is widely recognised, mainly because they are evaluated against societal and global standards. The country is resource-rich in Oil and

gas, and the ongoing debates on whether the national and foreign business investors have genuine motives to back sustainability add complexity to the KSA's sustainability plan. While the attempt to reconcile its ESG goals, notably those related to human rights, political freedoms and economic opportunities, generates questions regarding the possible attractiveness of KSA as an investment destination. Unlike the government's plans to create an ESG-inclusive mechanism and build a more democratic environment and inclusive communities, the process still faces certain problems. Women's human rights have progressed in several years, though the impact of this improvement on investor perception has mainly been positive. However, similar incidents as the Khashoggi incident have brought these issues into the debate, and hence, these have spurred scepticism, especially among Western investors. Advancing KSA on the road to development, it should proceed with this process very carefully by putting the ESG issues in harmony with the economic reality under the conditions of globalisation.

The theory of agency, stakeholders, legitimacy, and signalling drives the adoption of ESG investing in KSA. These methodologies give insights into the logic behind the incorporation of ESG principles, which implies that the objectives should be set to fulfil stakeholders' expectations for the sustainability of the business operations. An ESG-compliant investment ecosystem in KSA demonstrates an increasing recognition of factors influencing social, environmental, and governance, as revealed in the rules and regulations promoting corporate governance and transparency. However, the studies in the existing literature present controversial results on the correlation between ESG activities and sustainability outcomes. In contrast, a more pronounced relationship characterises the business environment in the KSA. Environmental sustainability can have an impact on financial performance. Besides, the costs and benefits are inseparable; however, on the other hand, both positive and negative correlations are found between social sustainability performance and CSR practices.

The relationship between ESG practices and Entrepreneurial Intentions at the Sustainability level in KSA presents a complex and varied landscape. Many previous studies report conflicting results, and some suggest that the stakeholders of ESG (SMEs and large businesses) consider ESG materiality the same. In contrast, others, particularly

SMEs, present a negative relationship between ESG and sustainability performance. Different stances indicate the complexity of the matter as they are driven by resource scarcity, investor opinion, and entrepreneurial role in sustainability. Despite the varying conclusions, the ESG factors turned out to be important in relation to sustainable intentions and outcomes in entrepreneurship in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Utilising international organisations, internal shareholders' interests, and the positive GDP effects of foreign investment, ESG's influence shows how the relationship between ESG and sustainability is complicated in the Saudi Arabian business environment. Current research and collaborations with stakeholders play a crucial role in addressing the complexity and attempting to realise entrepreneurship, which aligns with Saudi Vision 2030's objectives.

Many external and internal elements are the main features that affect entrepreneurial intention toward sustaining business in KSA. Factors such as risk perception, personal beliefs and values, and expertise intrinsically constitute the main ones. Regarding environmental sustainability, the government especially values entrepreneurs built based on such a concept. Thus, the environment is created for doing business in their favour. The highly active role of the KSA in projects such as training, teaching, and helping entrepreneurs with sustainability knowledge shows that it places great importance on people's practice of sustainable behaviour. Entrepreneurial intentions are based on multiple factors: regional stability, available technological support, financial resources, consumer awareness, cultural norms, government regulations, and trade barriers. The technology, favourable financial systems, and policies of KSA encourage people to perform sustainable actions. The developing cultural landscape struck out, rendering its social reforms corresponding to the global dialect for inclusivity and sustainability instead of adding the country's attractiveness to investors. Whereas regional instability and trade barriers are Saudi Arabia's challenges, its membership in the WTO stands for open market principles.

There is a consensus that CSR has a mixed relationship with financial performance in KSA based on the discrepancies in the literature. The relationship between CSR and financial performance is investigated with the help of the three studies that argue for an affirmative, no, and negative correlation. The problem under consideration is being

treated in detail. Corporate social responsibility practices in the KSA are guided by two crucial factors: profit and company size. Both factors affect the altering nature of corporate social responsibility in the region. Case studies offer diverse viewpoints, with most literature providing evidence for an advantage while others have no relationship or disadvantages. This paper investigates the validity of ESG scores to examine sustainable operations in KSA from a local lens. The study used ROA and ROE as financial performance metrics. These measures demonstrate the advantages and problems of the KSA's flexible economy that employs these indicators for inversion choices.

7.3. Overall Conclusion

The research brought out the need for more adequate management of diverse industries. It showed that the shortcomings provide a basis for improving the internal control structures, formulating a strategic plan, and engaging the stakeholders. The study is also confronted with the conflicting relationship between sustainability and the immediate financial rewards; however, the study reveals the critical part that sustainable practices can play in the companies of KSA in not only increasing the companies' economic efficiencies but also ensuring the companies' conformity with the global standards of ESG. This is explained by the fact that this research highlighted a relevant link between management and sustainable business methods. The complexities of entrepreneurial aspirations and the sustainability of KSA necessitate exploring the areas that require attention and continuous partnerships to de-mystify the areas and promote sustainable practices that align with the objectives of Saudi Vision 2030.

7.4. Further Research Suggestions

Future studies should develop standardized ESG methods as there currently is no consistent approach among the rating agencies, which means using different methods to

measure the same variable. Many organizations are responsible for grading companies' ESG criteria. However, there is a difference in the criteria and the source data, which results in a difference in the scores. Regulatory authorities, academia, industry stakeholders, and rating agencies can be used to develop standard rules and principles for assessing sustainability initiatives. This will demand the implementation of suitable mechanisms to identify the metrics and indicators for each ESG dimension (environmental, social, and governance) and create appropriate systems that will collect data, analyze them and report their results.

In future research, the need to assess long-term financial outcomes and performances of sustainability programs should be emphasized so that there is not only a longitudinal analysis but also an evaluation of how the performance of key financial indicators is influenced by holding investments in environmental, social, and governance practices. Apart from that, research planned for the future includes gauging the long-term effect of sustainability initiatives through ESG metrics and the prism of traditional financial performance. Unlike ESG ratings that give an idea of companies' sustainability performance, they may not be exhaustive in explaining the potential value the companies will create in the future. The in-depth follow-up studies of the companies which implement sustainability initiatives and the financial results over a long period may be the key to a more complete picture of the impact of sustainability on financial performance. Through the analysis, scientists can see how consistent investments in environmental management, social responsibility, and corporate governance influence performance measures such as profitability, shareholder value, and market competitiveness.

Conducting sector-specific analyses of ESG performance and its impact on financial performance could offer valuable insights for future research. Sustainability issues and opportunities in different industries may be different due to specific factors in the sectors, and their performance may be different in these industries. Using industry-specific traits in constructing ESG metrics and models can enable the inclusion of factors that influence performance. Let us take an example of an industry like manufacturing and a tech company. Their environmental impact will be different, and their social impact will be affected by factors such as labour practices and supply chain management. Sector-

specific analyses can lead to identifying effective strategies, benchmarks for results and calls for actions that help achieve sustainability goals.

Future research on entrepreneurial intentions and sustainability could explore the development of dynamic ESG rating methodologies that adapt to evolving sustainability trends and best practices. Companies' SES ratings that are calculated by conventional methods take static data sets and periodic reviews, which might review and overlook real-time changes in a company's sustainability performance. Using real-time data, predictive analytics methods, and dynamic modelling approaches can take dynamic ESG ratings to a more current and insightful level as they can give a forward-looking assessment of the companies' sustainability performance. The same can be done using machine learning algorithms for remote studies of news articles, social media posts, etc., which serve to discover emerging sustainability threats and business opportunities. Analyzing the process of the integration of qualitative valuations with stakeholder involvement can enhance the accuracy and reach of ESG rating tools in sustainable evaluation. By bringing in employees, customers, investors, or any other stakeholders, ESG ratings would be necessary to be dynamic and give a more comprehensive and balanced view of companies' sustainability practices and performance.

Employing qualitative methodologies such as interviews, case studies, and ethnography alongside quantitative analysis allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the interplay among entrepreneurial intentions, sustainable practices, and financial returns. Future research on entrepreneurial intentions and sustainability will compare quantitative approaches that provide us with different statistical insights into the relations between different variables with qualitative methods that allow us to understand the reasons, thoughts and actions behind these relations. It becomes evident that both of them have their advantages. Practising ESG data integration into financial metrics and ESG scores is combined with qualitative research to reveal more factors influencing the companies' sustainability performance. With this blended approach, a deeper understanding and a more complete and whole analysis will be achieved. Also, researching some studies in mixed-method designs, such as sequential explanatory or convergent designs, is an excellent chance because, through triangulating the data from the quantitative and the

qualitative findings, the validity and reliability of the research conclusions will be increased.

List of References

Abdelwahed, N. A. (2022). Developing entrepreneurial sustainability among Saudi Arabia's university students. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 11890–11898.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/su141911890>

Abdelwahed, Nadia A., Al Doghan, M. A., Saraih, U. N., & Soomro, B. A. (2023). Green Entrepreneurship in Saudi Arabia: Shaping the landscape of the greener economy. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 30(7), 1352–1376.

<https://doi.org/10.1108/jsbed-05-2023-0239>

Abdulhaq, A. S., & Muhamed, N. A. (2022). Extent of Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure and Its Determinants: Evidence from Kingdom of Saudia Arabia. *South East Asia Journal of Contemporary Business, Economics and Law*, 7(1), 40-47.

Aidis, R., Estrin, S., & Mickiewicz, T. (2008). Institutions and entrepreneurship development in Russia: A comparative perspective. *Journal of business Venturing*, 23(6), 656-672.

Ajina, A. S., Japutra, A., Nguyen, B., Syed Alwi, S. F., & Al-Hajla, A. H. (2020). The importance of CSR initiatives in building customer support and loyalty: Evidence from Saudi Arabia. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 31(3), 691-713.

Al Helaly, H. (2023, September 7). Why Saudi Arabia is the Future Frontier for Global Entrepreneurs. *The Entrepreneur*. Retrieved February 11, 2024, from <https://www.entrepreneur.com/science-technology/why-saudi-arabia-is-the-goldmine-for-global-entrepreneurs/457842#:~:text=Global%20crossroads%20and%20a%20growing%20business%20ecosystem&text=Recognizing%20the%20value%20of%20entrepreneurial,welcomes%20innovators%20with%20open%20arms.>

- Ala'Eddin Mohammad Khalaf Ahmad, O., Alsharqi, Z., Al-Borie, H. M., Mohammed, M., & Ashoor, A. S. A. O. (2020). Corporate social responsibility and brand image: an empirical investigation of private sector hospitals in Saudi Arabia. *Int. Bus. Res*, 9, 91.
- Al-Alqam, M.S., Rehman, A.U., & Alsultan, M. (2022). Study of Saudi Arabian manufacturing and service organization sustainability and future research directions. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1026, 012004.
- Al-Hadi, A., Taylor, G., & Al-Yahyaee, K. H. (2020). Ruling family political connections and risk reporting: evidence from the GCC. *The International Journal of Accounting*, 51(4), 504-524.
- Alharbi, R. K. (2023). Saudi Arabia's small and medium enterprises (SMES) sector post-Covid-19 recovery: stakeholders' perception on investment sustainability. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 31(6), 2222-2238.
- Al-Jalahma, A., Al-Fadhel, H., Al-Muhanadi, M., & Al-Zaimoor, N. (2020). Environmental, social, and governance (ESG) disclosure and firm performance: Evidence from GCC banking sector. *2020 International Conference on Decision Aid Sciences and Application (DASA)*.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/dasa51403.2020.9317210>
- Al-Janadi, Y., Abdul Rahman, R., & Alazzani, A. (2016). Does government ownership affect corporate governance and corporate disclosure? Evidence from Saudi Arabia. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 31(8/9), 871-890.
- Al-Janadi, Y., Rahman, R.A., & Haj Omar, N. (2013). Corporate Governance Mechanisms and Voluntary Disclosure in Saudi Arabia. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4, 25–35.
- Al-Malkawi, H.A.N., & Javid, S. (2018). Corporate social responsibility and financial performance in Saudi Arabia: Evidence from Zakat contribution.

- Almaqtari, F. A., Elsheikh, T., Abdelkhair, F., & Mazrou, Y. S. A. (2023). The impact of Corporate Environmental Disclosure Practices and board attributes on sustainability: Empirical evidence from Asia and Europe. *Heliyon*, 9(8). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e18453>
- Almubarak, W. I., Chebbi, K., & Ammer, M. A. (2023). Unveiling the connection among ESG, Earnings Management, and financial distress: Insights from an emerging market. *Sustainability*, 15(16), 12348. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151612348>
- Alofi, N. (2020). Corporate social responsibility in Saudi Arabia: perception, disclosure and impact on firm performance.
- Alotaibi, K. (2021). Determinants and consequences of CSR disclosure quantity and quality: evidence from Saudi Arabia.
- Al-Samhan, M. A. (2023). Factors Affect the Social Responsibility among Universities in Saudi Arabia: The Role of Government Support. *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, 20, 61-69.
- Alsayegh, M.F., Abdul Rahman, R., & Hodayoun, S. (2020). Corporate economic, environmental, and social sustainability performance transformation through ESG disclosure. *Sustainability*, 12(9), 3910.
- Alshaikh, L., Hamas, Y.M., & Khan, M. (2021). Implementation of CSR programs in Saudi SMES. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 18, 857–865.
- Alshareef, M. N. Z., & Sandhu, K. (2021). Integration of corporate social responsibility (CSR) into corporate governance: new model, structure and practice: a case study of Saudi company. *European Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research*, 3(5), 1-19.
- Alshehri, A., & Solomon, J. (2012). The Evolution of Corporate Governance in Saudi Arabia. In *Proceedings of the British Accounting and Finance Association (BAFA) 2012 Conference*, Brighton, UK, 17–19 April 2012.

- Alsheikh, A. H. (2023). Impact of human and social board capital on the level of sustainability reporting: Evidence from Saudi Arabia. *Sustainability*, 16(1), 15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16010015>
- Alwakid, W., Aparicio, S., & Urbano, D. (2020). Cultural antecedents of Green Entrepreneurship in Saudi Arabia: An institutional approach. *Sustainability*, 12(9), 3673. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12093673>
- Alwakid, W., Aparicio, S., & Urbano, D. (2021). The influence of green entrepreneurship on sustainable development in Saudi Arabia: The role of formal institutions. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(10), 5433.
- Amuah, J. (2023). Overcoming Corporate Disaster by Leveraging the Proactive Power of Enterprise Risk Management. *Available at SSRN 4624088*.
- An example from eastern european countries”, Economic Science Series, 31 (1). *Annals of the University of Oradea*
- Antoncic, M. (2019). Why sustainability? Because risk evolves and risk management should too. *Journal of Risk Management in Financial Institutions*, 12(3), 206-216.
- Arab News, (2023, March 12). Saudi Arabia calls for a balanced approach to ESG investment. *Arab News*. Retrieved February 9, 2024, from <https://www.arabnews.com/node/2267256/business-economy>.
- Arayssi, M., Jizi, M., & Tabaja, H. H. (2020). The impact of board composition on the level of ESG disclosures in GCC countries. *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal*, 11(1), 137–161. <https://doi.org/10.1108/sampj-05-2018-0136>
- Atkins, J., Doni, F., Gasperini, A., Artuso, S., La Torre, I., & Sorrentino, L. (2022). Exploring the effectiveness of sustainability measurement: Which ESG metrics will survive covid-19? *Journal of Business Ethics*, 185(3), 629–646. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-022-05183-1>

- Aupperle, K., Carroll, A., & Hatfield, J. (2022). An empirical examination of the relationship between corporate social responsibility and Profitability. *Academy of Management Journal*, 28, 446–463.
- Badkook, R., & Gazzaz, H. (2019). The Determinants of the CSRD Categories: Empirical Evidence from Saudi Arabia. *The International Journal of Business & Management*.
- Bamahros, H.M., Alquhaif, A., Qasem, A., Wan-Hussin, W.N., Thomran, M., Al-Duais, S.D., Shukeri, S.N., & Khojally, H.M. (2022). Corporate governance mechanisms and ESG reporting: Evidence from the Saudi Stock Market. *Sustainability*, 14, 6202. [CrossRef]
- Barauskaite, G., & Streimikiene, D. (2020). Corporate Social Responsibility and financial performance of companies: The puzzle of concepts, definitions and assessment methods. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 28(1), 278–287. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2048>
- Barbagila, M., Buttice, V., Giudici, G., Mendy, J., Sarker, T., Sharma, G.D., & Zutshi, A. (2021). Supporting SMEs in Sustainable Strategy Development Post-COVID-19: Challenges and Policy Agenda for the G20. Ph.D. Diss, Institute of Management Studies Ambika Zutshi Department of Management, Faculty of Business and Law, Deakin University.
- Barbuscia, D., Saba, Y., & Azhar, S. (2021, November 16). Insight: Saudi Arabia's race to attract investment dogged by scepticism. *Reuters*. Retrieved February 10, 2024, from <https://www.reuters.com/business/energy/saudi-arabias-race-attract-investment-dogged-by-scepticism-2021-11-16/>.
- Ben Fatma, H., & Chouaibi, J. (2021). Corporate governance and CSR disclosure: Evidence from European financial institutions. *International Journal of Disclosure and Governance*, 1-16.

- Boffo, R., & Patalano, R. (2020). ESG investing: practices, progress and challenges. *Éditions OCDE, Paris*. <https://www.oecd.org/finance/ESG-Investing-Practices-Progress-Challenges.pdf>
- Bowen, H.R. (2021). *Social Responsibility of the Businessman* (No. 3). Harper: New York, NY, USA.
- Brocke, J.V., Recker, J., & Seidel, S. (2022). *Green Business Process Management: Towards the Sustainable Enterprise*. Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 14, 32–50.
- Carroll, A. (2020). A three-dimensional conceptual model of corporate performance. *Academy of Management Review*, 4, 497–505.
- Carroll, A.B. (2022). Corporate social responsibility evolution of a definitional construct. *Business & Society*, 38, 268–295.
- Casielles, J. (2019). Roe, Roce, Beneficio Económico y eva (return on equity, return on capital employed, economic benefit and economic added value). *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3394255>
- Chebbi, K., & Ammer, M. A. (2022). Board composition and ESG disclosure in Saudi Arabia: The moderating role of Corporate Governance Reforms. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 12173. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912173>
- Chen, L., Yuan, T., Cebula, R. J., Shuangjin, W., & Foley, M. (2021). Fulfillment of ESG responsibilities and firm performance: a zero-sum game or mutually beneficial. *Sustainability*, 13(19), 10954.
- Chen, S., Song, Y., & Gao, P. (2023). Environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance and financial outcomes: Analyzing the impact of ESG on financial performance. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 345, 118829.

- Clément, A., Robinot, É., & Trespeuch, L. (2022). Improving ESG scores with Sustainability Concepts. *Sustainability*, *14*(20), 13154.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su142013154>
- Clément, A., Robinot, É., & Trespeuch, L. (2023). The use of ESG scores in Academic Literature: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jec-10-2022-0147>
- Coelho, R., Jayantilal, S., & Ferreira, J. J. (2023). The impact of social responsibility on corporate financial performance: A systematic literature review. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*.
- Cronan, J. (2022). ESG for Small Business—A Risk or an Opportunity Post COVID-19.
- D’Orazio, P. (2023). Navigating financial stability through the dual challenges of climate change and pandemics. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, *65*, 101386.
- Delai, I., & Takahashi, S. (2022). Sustainability measurement system: A reference model proposal. *Social Responsibility Journal*, *32*, 438–471. [CrossRef]
- Demirel, P., Li, Q.C., Rentocchini, F., & Tamvada, J.P. (2019). Born to be green: New insights into the economics and management of green entrepreneurship. *Small Business Economics*, *52*, 759–771.
- development in the 21st century. Emerald publishing limited.
- Dhaliwal, A. (2016). “Role of entrepreneurship in economic development”, *International Journal*
- Diez-Cañamero, B., Bishara, T., Otegi-Olaso, J. R., Minguéz, R., & Fernández, J. M. (2020). Measurement of Corporate Social Responsibility: A Review of Corporate Sustainability Indexes, rankings and ratings. *Sustainability*, *12*(5), 2153.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su12052153>

- Dkhili, H., & Dhiab, L.B. (2019). Corporate social responsibility and financial performance: The case of the Saudi companies. *International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences*, 6(9), 85-92.
- Dorfleitner, G., Halbritter, G., & Nguyen, M. (2015). Measuring the level and risk of corporate responsibility – an empirical comparison of different ESG rating approaches. *Journal of Asset Management*, 16(7), 450–466.
<https://doi.org/10.1057/jam.2015.31>
- Drempetic, S., Klein, C., & Zwergel, B. (2019). The influence of firm size on the ESG score: Corporate Sustainability Ratings under review. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 167(2), 333–360. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-019-04164-1>
- Dunn, J., Fitzgibbons, S., & Pomorski, L. (2022). Assessing risk through environmental, social and governance exposures. *Journal of Investment Management*, 16(1), 4-17.
- Eldaia, M. (2020). The relationship between Muslim directors on board of Directors and Audit Committee characteristics on performance evidence from Jordan. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3751808>
- Eliwa, Y., Aboud, A., & Saleh, A. (2021). ESG practices and the cost of debt: Evidence from EU countries. *Critical Perspectives on Accounting*, 79, 102097.
- entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intentions among university students: ADHD symptoms as a moderator”, *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, Vol. 15 No. 2, pp. 473-495.
- Fama, E.F., & Jensen, M.C. (2018). Separation of Ownership and Control. *Journal of Law and Economics*, 26, 301–325.
- Federation of Korean Industries. (2006). 2021 White Paper on the Society Contribution of Major Firms and Company Foundations. FKI Media Co., Ltd.: Seoul, Korea.

- Fernandes, C., Veiga, P.M., Ferreira, J., & Hughes, M. (2021). Green growth versus economic growth: Do sustainable technology transfer and innovations lead to an imperfect choice? *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 16, 2021–2037.
- Finta, M. A., & Ornelas, J. R. H. (2022). Commodity return predictability: Evidence from implied variance, skewness, and their risk premia☆☆. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 79, 101569.
- Firmansyah, E. A., Umar, U. H., & Jibril, R. S. (2023). Investigating the effect of ESG disclosure on firm performance: The case of Saudi Arabian listed firms. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11(2), 2287923.
- Gafar, A. (2022). “The role of entrepreneurship in achieving sustainable development goals:
- Galankashi, M. R., & Rafiei, F. M. (2021). Financial performance measurement of supply chains: A Review. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 71(5), 1674–1707. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijppm-11-2019-0533>
- Gholami, A., Sands, J., & Shams, S. (2022). Corporates’ sustainability disclosures impact on cost of capital and idiosyncratic risk. *Mediterranean Accounting Research*.
- Girin, J. (2011). Empirical Analysis of Management Situations: Elements of Theory and Method 1. *European Management Review*, 8, 197–212.
- Grabinska, B., Kedzior, M., Kedzior, D., & Grabinski, K. (2021). The impact of corporate governance on the capital structure of companies from the energy industry. The case of Poland. *Energies*, 14(21), 7412.
- Gregory, A. J., Atkins, J. P., Midgley, G., & Hodgson, A. M. (2020). Stakeholder identification and engagement in problem structuring interventions. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 283(1), 321-340.
- growth: The experience of developed and developing countries in entrepreneurship and

- Habbash, M. S. (2017). Corporate social responsibility disclosure, financial performance and firm value: the case of Saudi Arabia. *Arab Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 24(1).
- Halawi, A. (2008). *Power Matters: A Survey of GCC Boards*. Hawkamah: Dubai, United Arab Emirates.
- Hassan, B. A.; Azeez, A. A. & Abosedo, A. J. (2022). Entrepreneurship and sustainable development. Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Hallmark University, Ijebu-Itele, Ogun State, Nigeria, 62.
- Hazen, T. L. (2020). Social Issues in the Spotlight: The Increasing Need to Improve Publicly-Held Companies' CSR and ESG Disclosures. *U. Pa. J. Bus. L.*, 23, 740.
- Heo, M.O., & Chung, K.H. (2019). A study on relationship between CSR performance and corporate value: Focus on mediation effect of corporate reputation. *Journal of Industrial Economics and Business*, 23, 749–771.
- Hübel, B., & Scholz, H. (2020). Integrating sustainability risks in asset management: the role of ESG exposures and ESG ratings. *Journal of Asset Management*, 21(1), 52-69.
- Idrissi, A.E. (2021). From Necessity to Opportunity: The Case for Impact Investing in the Arab World. In *Social Entrepreneurship in the Middle East: Volume 1* (pp. 178-207). London: Palgrave Macmillan UK.
- International evidence”, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 128, 46-55.
- ISO. (2010). Corporate social responsibility through the lens of ISO standards. *Business Excellence and Management*, 2(4), 56-66.
- Issa, A. (2021). The factors influencing corporate social responsibility disclosure in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 11(10), 1–19.

- Issa, A., Zaid, M.A.A., Hanaysha, J.R., & Gull, A.A. (2022). An Examination of Board Diversity and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure: Evidence from Banking Sector in the Arabian Gulf Countries. *International Journal of Accounting Information Management*, 30, 22–46.
- lyigün, N. O. (2015). “What could entrepreneurship do for sustainable development? A corporate social responsibility-based approach”, *Procedia-social and Behavioral Sciences*, 195, 1226-1231.
- Izcan, D., & Bektas, E. (2022). The Relationship between ESG Scores and Firm-Specific Risk of Eurozone Banks. *Sustainability*, 14(14), 8619.
- Jamali, D., & Mirshak, R. (2019). Corporate social responsibility: Theory and practice in a developing country context. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 72, 243–262.
- Jang, J.I., & Choi, H.S. (2020). The relation between corporate social responsibility and financial performance. *Daehan Journal of Business*, 23, 633–648.
- Jensen, M.C., & Meckling, W.H. (1976). Theory of the Firm: Managerial Behavior, Agency Costs and Ownership Structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3, 305–360.
- John, O. (2023). “Factors constraining the growth and survival of smes in nigeria”, *Management*
- Johnson, M. P., & Schaltegger, S. (2020). Entrepreneurship for sustainable development: A review and multilevel causal mechanism framework. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 44(6), 1141-1173.
- Jung, Y.S. (2022). Prepare for corporate social responsibility (CSR). *LG Weekly Economic*, 858, 3–7.
- Karwowski, M., & Raulinajtys-Grzybek, M. (2021). The application of corporate social responsibility (CSR) actions for mitigation of environmental, social, corporate

- governance (ESG) and reputational risk in integrated reports. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 28(4), 1270-1284.
- Katmon, N., Mohamad, Z.Z., Mat Norwani, N., & Al Farooque, O. (2019). Comprehensive Board Diversity and Quality of Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure: Evidence from an Emerging Market. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 157, 447–481.
- Khaled, R., Ali, H., & Mohamed, E.K. (2021). The Sustainable Development Goals and corporate sustainability performance: Mapping, extent and determinants. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 311, 127599.
- Khan, E., Dewan, M., & Chowdhury, M. (2022). Reflective or formative measurement model of sustainability factor? A three industry comparison. *Corporate Ownership & Control*, 13, 83–92.
- Khan, M.R. (2023). Mapping entrepreneurship ecosystem of Saudi Arabia. *World Review of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 47, 28–54.
- Kibsey, S., Kibsey, S. D., Addas, A., & Krosinsky, C. (2020). The Evolving Risk Management Opportunity and Thinking Sustainability First. *Ecological, Societal, and Technological Risks and the Financial Sector*, 123-139.
- Kim, S., & Yoon, A. (2020). Analyzing active managers' commitment to ESG: Evidence from United Nations principles for responsible investment. Available at SSRN, 3555984.
- Korea Nonprofit Research Academy. (2020). Development Research Report of Corporate Social Contribution Indicators. FKI Media Co., Ltd.: Seoul, Korea.
- Kotsantonis, S., & Serafeim, G. (2019). Four things no one will tell you about ESG Data. *Journal of Applied Corporate Finance*, 31(2), 50–58.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jacf.12346>

- Kramer, M.R., & Porter, M. (2011). *Creating Shared Value*. FSG: Boston, MA, USA, 17.
- Lasana, T. (2022). *Relationship Between Risk Exposure, Volatility Forecasting, and Financial Performance of Hedge Funds* (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University).
- Li, J., & Wu, D. (2020). Do corporate social responsibility engagements lead to real environmental, social, and governance impact?. *Management Science*, 66(6), 2564-2588.
- Lipton, M., Neff, D. A., Brownstein, A. R., Rosenblum, S. A., Emmerich, A. O., & Fain, S. L. (2021). Risk management and the board of directors. *Bank and Corporate Governance Law Reporter*, 45(6), 793-799.
- Liu, X. (2019). The role of enterprise risk management in sustainable decision-making: A cross-cultural comparison. *Sustainability*, 11(10), 2939.
- Luo, W., Tian, Z., Fang, X., & Deng, M. Can good ESG performance reduce stock price crash risk? Evidence from Chinese listed companies. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*.
- Lyttle, C. (2022, September 22). FDI in the Middle East and Africa in 2021: The state of play. *Investment Monitor*. Retrieved February 10, 2024, from <https://www.investmentmonitor.ai/fdi-data/fdi-middle-east-africa-2021-state-of-play/?cf-view>.
- Maignan, I., Ferrell, O.C., & Ferrell, L. (2021). A stakeholder model for implementing social responsibility in marketing. *European Journal of Marketing*, 39, 956–977.
- Mamede, P., & Gomes, C. F. (2022). Corporate sustainability measurement in service organizations: A case study from Portugal. *Environmental Quality Management*, 23(3), 49-73.

- Manogna, R. L., & Mishra, A. K. (2021). Measuring financial performance of Indian Manufacturing Firms: Application of Decision tree algorithms. *Measuring Business Excellence*, 26(3), 288–307. <https://doi.org/10.1108/mbe-05-2020-0073>
- Mansour, A.-A. (2023, March 20). Why Saudi Arabia Remains Bullish on FDI and Attracting Large-Scale Foreign Investments. *LinkedIn*. February 10, 2024, <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/why-saudi-arabia-remains-bullish-fdi-attracting-foreign-al-ajmi>
- Masoud, N., & Vij, A. (2021). Factors influencing corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSR) by Libyan state-owned enterprises (SOEs). *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1), 1859850.
- Massenbach, U. (2024, January 21). How Saudi Arabia is reshaping transportation infrastructure amid climate change challenges. *LinkedIn*. February 10, 2024, https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/how-saudi-arabia-reshaping-transportation-amid-change-von-massenbach-nsqyf?trk=article-ssr-frontend-pulse_more-articles_related-content-card
- Mentor, M. (2016). The effects of corporate social responsibility on financial performance.
- Mohammadi, S., Saeidi, H., & Naghshbandi, N. (2020). The Impact of Board and Audit Committee Characteristics on Corporate Social Responsibility: Evidence from the Iranian Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Production Performance Management*, 1, 2207–2236.
- MOHAMMED, S. (2022). *THE EFFECT OF MARKETING INTELLIGENCE ON SALES PERFORMANCE OF PRIVATE BANKS IN ADDIS ABABA* (Doctoral dissertation, ST. MARY'S UNIVERSITY).
- Morsing, M., & Perrini, F. (2009). CSR in SMEs: Do SMEs matter for the CSR agenda? *Business Ethics: A European Review*, 18, 1–6.

- Muthuswamy, V. V., & Yunusova, R. (2023). Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure and Bankruptcy Financial Risks: Moderating Role of Corporate Governance Index. *Cuadernos de Economía*, 46(132), 69-78.
- NACD. (2019). *2019–2020 NACD Public Company Governance Survey*. NACD: Arlington, VA, USA.
- Nirino, N., Santoro, G., Miglietta, N., & Quaglia, R. (2021). Corporate controversies and company's financial performance: Exploring the moderating role of ESG practices. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 162, 120341. No. 4, pp. 585-594.
- Of Scientific Research and Management, 4 (6), 4262-4269.
- Omair Alotaibi, K., & Hussainey, K. (2020). Determinants of CSR disclosure quantity and quality: Evidence from non-financial listed firms in Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Disclosure and Governance*, 13(4), 364-393.
- Omri, A. (2022). "Entrepreneurship, sectoral outputs and environmental improvement:
- O'Neill, K., & Gibbs, D. (2020). Rethinking green entrepreneurship—Fluid narratives of the green economy. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 48(9), 1727-1749.
- Park, Y.K. (2023). Evaluating the performance of trading strategies based on corporate social responsibility. *Korea Journal of Business Administration*, 26, 891–907.
- Parrot, K. W., & Tierney, B. X. (2022). Integrated reporting, stakeholder engagement, and balanced investing at American Electric Power. *Journal of Applied Corporate Finance*, 24(2), 27-37.
- Perrini, F.; Russo, A. & Tencati, A. (2022). "CSR Strategies of smes and large firms: Evidence from italy", *Journal of Business Ethics*. 74, 285-300.

- Porter, M. E. & Kramer, M. R. (2022). "Strategy and society: The link between competitive advantage and corporate social responsibility", *Harvard Business Review*, December, 78-94.
- PROSPERO. (n.d.). Guidance notes for registering a systematic review protocol with PROSPERO.
<https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPERO/documents/Registering%20a%20review%20on%20PROSPERO.pdf>
- PRISMA. (n.d). PRISMA statement. <http://www.prisma-statement.org/PRISMAStatement/>
- Princigalli, S. (2023, October 9). Investing in Saudi Arabia: Unlocking Opportunities in a Thriving Economy. *LinkedIn*. February 10, 2024,
<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/investing-saudi-arabia-unlocking-opportunities-sabrina-princigalli>
- Rajesh, R., & Rajendran, C. (2019). Relating environmental, social, and governance scores and sustainability performances of firms: An empirical analysis. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 29(3), 1247–1267.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2429>
- Rakipi, R., & D'Onza, G. (2023). The involvement of internal audit in environmental, social, and governance practices and risks: Stakeholders' salience and insights from audit committees and chief executive officers. *International Journal of Auditing*.
- Ramady, M.A., & Saeed, J. (2021). Foreign direct investment: A strategic move toward sustainable free enterprise and economic development in Saudi Arabia. *Thunderbird International Business Review*, 49(1), 37–56.
- Ramón-Llorens, M.C., García-Meca, E., & Pucheta-Martínez, M.C. (2019). The Role of Human and Social Board Capital in Driving CSR Reporting. *Long Range Planning*, 52, 101846.

- Reber, B., Gold, A., & Gold, S. (2022). ESG disclosure and idiosyncratic risk in initial public offerings. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 179, 867–886.
- Research Review, 31 (2), 156-171.doi: 10.1108/409171111102786.
- Reuters, (2023, October 26). Saudi FDI reaches 6.2 billion riyals in Q2 2023. *Reuters*. Retrieved February 9, 2024, from [https://www.reuters.com/article/idUSS8N3B908A/#:~:text=DUBAI%2C%20Oct%2026%20\(Reuters\),economy%20ministry%20said%20on%20Thursday](https://www.reuters.com/article/idUSS8N3B908A/#:~:text=DUBAI%2C%20Oct%2026%20(Reuters),economy%20ministry%20said%20on%20Thursday).
- Robayo-Acuña, P. V., Martínez-Toro, G. M., Álvarez-Risco, A., Młodzianowska, S., Del-Aguila-Arcentales, S., & Rojas-Osorio, M. (2023). Intention of Green Entrepreneurship Among University Students in Colombia. In *Footprint and Entrepreneurship: Global Green Initiatives* (pp. 259-272). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
- Roh, H.K. (2011). *Examining Social Responsibility through ISO 26000*. Parkyoungsa: Seoul, Korea.
- Russo, A., & Perrini, F. (2010). Investigating stakeholder theory and social capital: CSR in large firms and SMEs. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 91, 207–221.
- Sadiq, M., Ngo, T. Q., Pantamee, A. A., Khudoykulov, K., Thi Ngan, T., & Tan, L. P. (2022). The role of environmental social and governance in Achieving Sustainable Development Goals: Evidence from ASEAN countries. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 36(1), 170–190. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677x.2022.2072357>
- Sadou, A., Alom, F., & Laluddin, H. (2017). Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures in Malaysia: Evidence from Large Companies. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 13, 177–202.
- Saleh, A. (2020). *Corporate social responsibility in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs): A Saudi Arabian perspective* (Doctoral dissertation, Cardiff University).

- Samargandi, N., A. Alghfais, M., & AlHuthail, H. M. (2022). Factors in Saudi FDI inflow. *SAGE Open*, 12(1), 3–38. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211067242>
- Sameer, I. (2021). Impact of corporate social responsibility on organization's financial performance: Evidence from Maldives public limited companies. *Future Business Journal*, 7(1), 1-21.
- Santos, S. C., & Liguori, E. W. (2020). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy and intentions: Outcome expectations as mediator and subjective norms as moderator. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 26(3), 400-415.
- Sarkar, A., Qian, L., Peau, A.K. and Shahriar, S. (2021), "Modeling drivers for successful adoption of green business: an interpretive structural modeling approach", *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, Vol. 28, pp. 1077-1096.
- Saudi Capital Market Authority. (2020). *Annual Report 2020*. Capital Market Authority: Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.
- Serafeim, G. (2020). Social-impact efforts that create real value. *Harvard Business Review*, 98, 38–48.
- Sergi, B. S.; Popkova, E. G.; Bogoviz, A. V. & Ragulina, J. V. (2019). Entrepreneurship and economic
- Sern, L.C., Zaima, A.F. and Foong, L.M. (2018), "Green skills for green industry: a review of literature", In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, Vol. 1019 No. 1, 012030. Sher, A., Mazhar, S., Zulfiqar, F., Wang, D. and Li, X. (2019), "Green entrepreneurial farming: a dream or reality?", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol. 220 No. 2019, pp. 1131-1142.
- Shin, Y. G. (2001). *Socially Responsible Management*; Kyungmoonsa: Seoul. Korea, 554.

- Solesvik, M.Z. (2013), "Entrepreneurial motivations and intentions: investigating the role of education major", *Education þ Training*, Vol. 55 No. 3, pp. 253-271.
- Soomro, B.A. and Shah, N. (2022), "Entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial self-efficacy, need for achievement and entrepreneurial intention among commerce students in Pakistan", *Education þ Training*, Vol. 64 No. 1, pp. 107-125.
- Soomro, B.A., Ghumro, I.A. and Shah, N. (2020a), "Green entrepreneurship inclination among the younger generation: an avenue towards a green economy", *Sustainable Development*, Vol. 28
- Soomro, B.A., Shah, N. and Anwar, S. (2018), "Determining the impact of entrepreneurial adversity and psychological capital on entrepreneurial resilience among entrepreneurs of Pakistan", *Journal of Asia Entrepreneurship and Sustainability*, Vol. 14 No. 2, pp. 95-116.
- Soomro, B.A., Shah, N. and Lashari, A.A. (2020b), "Assessment of entrepreneurial networking activities and perceived self-efficacy towards entrepreneurial success", *SALU-Commerce and Economics Review*, Vol. 6 No. 1, pp. 30-46.
- Steinhöfel, E., Galeitzke, M., Kohl, H., & Orth, R. (2019). Sustainability reporting in German manufacturing SMEs. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 33, 610–617.
- Stratton, S.J. (2021), "Population research: convenience sampling strategies", *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine*, Vol. 36 No. 4, pp. 373-374.
- Styles, C. and Seymour, R.G. (2006), "Opportunities for marketing researchers in international entrepreneurship", *International Marketing Review*, Vol. 23 No. 2, pp. 126-145.
- Sulphey, M.M., & Alkahtani, N. (2017). Economic security and sustainability through social entrepreneurship: The current Saudi scenario. *Journal of Security and Sustainability Issues*, 6(3).

- Taber, K.S. (2018), "The use of Cronbach's alpha when developing and reporting research instruments in science education", *Research in Science Education*, Vol. 48 No. 2018, pp. 1273-1296.
- Teja., N. (2023). Saudi Arabia's ESG profile: progress or PR?. FDI Intelligence. <https://www.fdiintelligence.com/content/feature/saudi-arabias-esg-profile-progress-or-pr-82788>
- Tien, N.H., Tien, N.V., Mai, N.P. and Duc, L.D.M. (2023), "Green entrepreneurship: a game changer in Vietnam business landscape", *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, Vol. 48 No. 4, pp. 408-431.
- Torpey, J. F. (2020). *The Influence of Regulatory Oversight on Environmental, Social, and Governance Ratings* (Doctoral dissertation, Franklin University).
- Touny, M. A., Qamar, K. A., & Alayis, M. M. H. (2021). Corporate social responsibility practices and their impact on sustainable development in Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Services, Economics and Management*, 12(2), 185-209.
- Tran, T.V.H., Duong, C.D., Nguyen, T.H., Tran, T.S.L. and Vu, T.N. (2023), "UPPS impulsivity,
- Turkina, E. and Thai, M.T.T (2013), "Social capital, networks, trust and immigrant entrepreneurship: a cross-country analysis", *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, Vol. 7 No. 2, pp. 108-124.
- Tuszynski, M.P. and Stansel, D. (2018), "Targeted state economic development incentives and entrepreneurship", *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Public Policy*, Vol. 7 No. 3, pp. 235-247.
- Umar, U. H., Firmansyah, E. A., Danlami, M. R., & Al-Faryan, M. A. (2023). Revisiting the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and ESG

- disclosures in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Accounting & Organizational Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jaoc-01-2023-0011>
- Urbano, D., Aparicio, S., & Audretsch, D. (2019). Twenty-five years of research on institutions, entrepreneurship, and economic growth: What has been learned? *Small Business Economics*, 53, 21–49.
- Vasilescu, M.D., Dimian, G.C. and Gradinaru, G.I. (2023), “Green entrepreneurship in challenging times: a quantitative approach for European countries”, *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istrazivanja*, Vol. 36 No. 1, pp. 1828-1847.
- Wagner, B. (2022). Implementing and managing economic, social and environmental efforts of business sustainability. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, 26(2), 195-213.
- Wennekers, S.; Van Stel, A.; Carree, M. & Thurik, r. (2010). “The relationship between entrepreneurship and economic development: is it u-shaped?”, *Foundations and Trends in Entrepreneurship*, 6 (3), 167-237.
- Yang, J.S., Yeo, Y.J., & Kwon, O.J. (2023). The effect of excellence in corporate social responsibility activities on accounting conservatism. *Korea Management Association Management Studies*, 43, 1937–1961.
- Yang, O. S., & Han, J. H. (2023). Assessing the effect of corporate esg management on corporate financial & market performance and export. *Sustainability*, 15(3), 2316.
- Yi, G. (2020). From green entrepreneurial intentions to green entrepreneurial behaviors: The role of university entrepreneurial support and external institutional support. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*.
- Zahraie, B., Everett, A.M., Walton, S., & Kirkwood, J. (2016). Environmental entrepreneurs facilitating change toward sustainability: A case study of the wine industry in New Zealand. *Small Enterprise Development*, 23, 39–57.

Zentner, L. (2023). ESG in Saudi Arabia: A kingdom-wide vision. *ESG Mena*. Retrieved February 9, 2024, from <https://esgmena.com/blog/2022/11/14/esg-in-saudi-arabia-a-kingdom-wide-vision%ef%bf%bc/>.

Ziolo, M. (Ed.). (2021). *Adapting and mitigating environmental, social, and governance risk in business*. IGI Global.

ANNEX

Annex 1: Corporate Data

Following is the data analysed collected from 17 KSA corporations in different sectors. The ESG-related data and management rating were collected from Sustainalytics, where the ROE, debt-to-assets and ROA data were collected from organisational reports and the WSJ.

Company	Sector	Ticker	ESG Score	ESG Risk Rating	Exposure	Management	Debt-To-Assets%	ROA%	ROE%
Saudi Arabian Oil Co	Oil & Gas Products/Services	2222	43.7	Severe	High	Average	15.77	25.66	46.62
Abdullah Al Othaim Markets Co	Food Retail	4001	29.4	Medium	Medium	Weak	30.22	19.98	77.8
Advanced Petrochemical Co	Chemicals	2330	27.8	Medium	Medium	Average	48.12	4.17	8.45
Al Dawaa Medical Services Co	Drug Retail	4163	19.5	Low	Low	Weak	58.54	7.16	29.31
Al Rajhi Bank	Banking	1120	25.3	Medium	Medium	Average	11.55	2.47	22.71
Almarai Co	Food Products	2280	32.3	High	High	Average	34.48	6	11.89
Arabian Cement Co	Building Materials/Products	3110	39.2	High	Medium	Weak	22.03	0.93	2.6
Middle East Healthcare Co	Healthcare Provision	4009	30.5	High	Low	Weak	49.8	1.78	5.73
Najran Cement Co	Building Materials/Products	3002	40.3	Severe	Medium	Weak	11.79	4.73	5.75
Riyad Bank	Banking	1010	28.7	Medium	Medium	Average	15.19	2.05	14.49
Saudi Arabian Mining Co	Mining	1211	49.4	Severe	High	Average	36.36	8.67	23.09
Saudi Arabia Refineries Co	Refiners/Pipeline	2030	50.3	Severe	Medium	Weak	26.16	5.6	5.66
Al-Jouf Agricultural Development Co	Food Products	6070	47.4	Severe	High	Weak	12.59	6.15	7.89
Saudi Electricity Co	Utilities	5110	36	High	High	Average	20.84	1.58	2.96
Saudi Awwal Bank	Banking	1060	27.7	Medium	Medium	Average	9.93	1.68	9.16
Mobile Telecommunications Co. Saudi Arabia	Telecominication	7030	25.1	Medium	Medium	Average	24.7	1.95	5.84
Elm Co. (Saudi Arabia)	Software & Services	7203	28.3	Medium	Medium	Weak	2.21	16.68	31.77

Annex 2: Descriptive Statistical Analysis

The frequency table below shows the frequencies of the level in the variables ESG risk rating, exposure, and management.

Frequency Table

		ESG Risk Rating			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	High	4	23.5	23.5	23.5
	Low	1	5.9	5.9	29.4
	Medium	7	41.2	41.2	70.6
	Severe	5	29.4	29.4	100.0
	Total	17	100.0	100.0	

		Exposure			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	High	5	29.4	29.4	29.4
	Low	2	11.8	11.8	41.2
	Medium	10	58.8	58.8	100.0
	Total	17	100.0	100.0	

		Management			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Average	9	52.9	52.9	52.9
	Weak	8	47.1	47.1	100.0
	Total	17	100.0	100.0	

The summary statistics table below shows the descriptive statistics of the numeral continuous data namely ESG score, Debt-t0-Aeests, ROA and ROE.

Descriptives**Descriptive Statistics**

	N Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness Statistic	Std. Error
ESG Score	17	19.5	50.3	34.171	9.3103	.492	.550
Debt-To-Assets%	17	2.21	58.54	25.3106	15.77959	.727	.550
ROA%	17	.93	25.66	6.8965	7.16830	1.691	.550
ROE%	17	2.60	77.80	18.3365	19.59619	2.053	.550
Valid N (listwise)	17						

Annex 3: Multinomial Regression Statistical Analysis, Impact of Management on Sustainable Business Practices

Following are the multinomial regression analysis output run for the variables management and ESG risk rating with management being the independent variable and ESG risk rating being the dependent variable.

Case Processing Summary

		N	Marginal Percentage
ESG Risk Rating	High	4	23.5%
	Low	1	5.9%
	Medium	7	41.2%
	Severe	5	29.4%
Management	Average	9	52.9%
	Weak	8	47.1%
Valid		17	100.0%
Missing		0	
Total		17	
Subpopulation		2	

Model Fitting Information

Model	Model Fitting		Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	Criteria				
	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.	
Intercept Only	13.793				
Final	10.936	2.857	3	.041	

Annex 4: Debt-to Assets Association with Financial Performance

The output below shows the regression model run with debt-to-assets being the independent variable and ROA being the dependent variable.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.129 ^a	.017	-.049	7.34130

a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt-To-Assets%

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.733	1	13.733	.255	.621 ^b
	Residual	808.420	15	53.895		
	Total	822.153	16			

a. Dependent Variable: ROA%

b. Predictors: (Constant), Debt-To-Assets%

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8.382	3.440		2.436	.028
	Debt-To-Assets%	-.059	.116	-.129	-.505	.621

a. Dependent Variable: ROA%

The output below shows the regression model run with debt-to-assets being the independent variable and ROE being the dependent variable.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.015 ^a	.000	-.066	20.23649

a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt-To-Assets%

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.441	1	1.441	.004	.953 ^b
	Residual	6142.730	15	409.515		
	Total	6144.172	16			

a. Dependent Variable: ROE%

b. Predictors: (Constant), Debt-To-Assets%

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	17.855	9.484		1.883	.079
	Debt-To-Assets%	.019	.321	.015	.059	.953

a. Dependent Variable: ROE%

Annex 5: Sustainable Business Practices Impact on Financial Performance

Below is the regression model output run for model 1 where ROA and ESG scores were the dependent and independent variables, respectively.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.169 ^a	.029	-.036	7.29683

a. Predictors: (Constant), ESG Score

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23.498	1	23.498	.441	.517 ^b
	Residual	798.655	15	53.244		
	Total	822.153	16			

a. Dependent Variable: ROA%

b. Predictors: (Constant), ESG Score

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.449	6.925		.354	.729
	ESG Score	.130	.196	.169	.664	.517

a. Dependent Variable: ROA%

Below is the regression model output run for model 1 where ROE and ESG scores were the dependent and independent variables, respectively.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.148 ^a	.022	-.043	20.01559

a. Predictors: (Constant), ESG Score

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	134.816	1	134.816	.337	.570 ^b
	Residual	6009.356	15	400.624		
	Total	6144.172	16			

a. Dependent Variable: ROE%

b. Predictors: (Constant), ESG Score

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	28.990	18.996		1.526	.148
	ESG Score	-.312	.537	-.148	-.580	.570

a. Dependent Variable: ROE%

Annex 6: PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram Used

Following is the PRISMA flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases, registers and other sources. The template was utilized when completing the study.

Annex 7: Studies

Title	Authors	Aim	Population	Sample size	Method
ESG for Small Business—A Risk or an Opportunity Post COVID-19	Cronan, J.	Investigate the implications of ESG for small businesses post-COVID-19.	Small businesses in various sectors	181	Literature review
ESG practices and the cost of debt: Evidence from EU countries	Eliwa, Y., Aboud, A., & Saleh, A.	Examine the relationship between ESG practices and cost of debt.	EU countries	303	Empirical analysis
ESG disclosure and idiosyncratic risk in initial public offerings	Reber, B., Gold, A., & Gold, S.	Explore the impact of ESG disclosure on idiosyncratic risk in IPOs.	Companies in IPO process	424	Empirical analysis
Fulfillment of ESG responsibilities	Chen, L., Yuan, T., Cebula, R. J.,	Investigate the relationship between ESG responsibilities	Various firms	557	Empirical analysis

and firm performance	Shuangjin, W., & Foley, M.	and firm performance.			
Environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance and financial outcomes	Chen, S., Song, Y., & Gao, P.	Analyze the impact of ESG performance on financial outcomes.	Various companies	689	Empirical analysis
Stakeholder identification and engagement in problem structuring interventions	Gregory, A. J., Atkins, J. P., Midgley, G., & Hodgson, A. M.	Study stakeholder identification and engagement in problem structuring interventions.	Various stakeholders	741	Literature review
A stakeholder model for implementing social responsibility in marketing	Maignan, I., Ferrell, O.C., & Ferrell, L.	Propose a stakeholder model for implementing social responsibility in marketing.	Marketing contexts	813	Conceptual framework development

Foreign direct investment: A strategic move toward sustainable free enterprise and economic development in Saudi Arabia	Ramady, M.A., & Saeed, J.	Investigate the role of FDI in sustainable economic development in Saudi Arabia.	Saudi Arabian context	857	Literature review
The application of corporate social responsibility (CSR) actions for mitigation of environmental, social, corporate governance (ESG) and reputational risk in integrated reports	Karwowski, M., & Raulinajtys-Grzybek, M.	Examine the use of CSR actions to mitigate ESG and reputational risks.	Various companies	903	Conceptual framework development
Corporate controversies and company's	Nirino, N., Santoro, G., Miglietta,	Investigate the moderating role of ESG practices on corporate	Various companies	917	Empirical analysis

financial performance	N., & Quaglia, R.	controversies and financial performance.			
The involvement of internal audit in environmental, social, and governance practices and risks	Rakipi, R., & D'Onza, G.	Explore the involvement of internal audit in ESG practices and risks.	Companies	925	Survey and interviews
Do corporate social responsibility engagements lead to real environmental, social, and governance impact?	Li, J., & Wu, D.	Examine the impact of CSR engagements on real ESG outcomes.	Various companies	934	Empirical analysis
Risk management and the board of directors	Lipton, M., Neff, D. A., Brownstein, A. R., Rosenblum, S. A., Emmerich,	Investigate the role of the board of directors in risk management.	Companies	939	Literature review

	A. O., & Fain, S. L.				
Assessing the effect of corporate ESG management on corporate financial & market performance and export	Yang, O. S., & Han, J. H.	Assess the impact of corporate ESG management on financial and market performance.	Various companies	941	Empirical analysis
The Influence of Regulatory Oversight on Environmental, Social, and Governance Ratings	Torpey, J. F.	Explore the influence of regulatory oversight on ESG ratings.	Companies	942	Literature review
Exploring the Bi-directional relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial	McWilliams & Siegel	Examine the relationship between CSR and financial performance in India.	Indian companies	943	Empirical analysis

performance in Indian context					
Sustainable business practices and firm's financial performance in islamic banking	Cho, A., Marimuthu, M., Hassan, R., & Mehreen.	Investigate the relationship between sustainable practices and financial performance in Islamic banking.	Islamic banking sector	944	Empirical analysis
The impact of board composition on the level of ESG disclosures in GCC countries	Arayssi, M., Jizi, M., & Tabaja, H. H.	Study the impact of board composition on ESG disclosures in GCC countries.	GCC countries	945	Empirical analysis
Green Entrepreneurship in Saudi Arabia: Shaping the landscape of the greener economy	Abdelwaheed, Nadia A., Al Doghan, M. A., Saraih, U. N., & Soomro, B. A.	Investigate green entrepreneurship's role in shaping Saudi Arabia's greener economy.	Saudi Arabian context	946	Literature review

Financial performance measurement of supply chains	Galankashi, M. R., & Rafiei, F. M.	Review financial performance measurement in supply chains.	Supply chain companies	947	Literature review
Exploring the relationship between risk exposure, volatility forecasting, and financial performance of hedge funds	Lasana, T.	Explore the relationship between risk exposure, volatility forecasting, and financial performance of hedge funds.	Hedge funds	947	Empirical analysis
The Relationship between ESG Scores and Firm-Specific Risk of Eurozone Banks	Izcan, D., & Bektas, E.	Investigate the relationship between ESG scores and firm-specific risk of Eurozone banks.	Eurozone banks	947	Empirical analysis
Assessing risk through environmental, social and	Dunn, J., Fitzgibbons, S., &	Assess risk through environmental, social, and	Various companies	947	Empirical analysis

governance exposures	Pomorski, L.	governance exposures.			
Navigating financial stability through the dual challenges of climate change and pandemics	D’Orazio, P.	Explore strategies for navigating financial stability amidst climate change and pandemics.	Financial institutions	947	Literature review
The impact of corporate governance on the capital structure of companies from the energy industry	Grabinska, B., Kedzior, M., Kedzior, D., & Grabinski, K.	Investigate the impact of corporate governance on the capital structure of energy companies.	Energy industry firms	947	Empirical analysis
Commodity return predictability: Evidence from implied variance, skewness, and their risk premia	Finta, M. A., & Ornelas, J. R. H.	Examine commodity return predictability using implied variance, skewness, and risk premia.	Commodity markets		

Exploring the relationship between risk exposure, volatility forecasting, and financial performance of hedge funds	Lasana, T.	Explore the relationship between risk exposure, volatility forecasting, and financial performance of hedge funds.	Hedge funds	947	Empirical analysis
The Relationship between ESG Scores and Firm-Specific Risk of Eurozone Banks	Izcan, D., & Bektas, E.	Investigate the relationship between ESG scores and firm-specific risk of Eurozone banks.	Eurozone banks	947	Empirical analysis
Assessing risk through environmental, social and governance exposures	Dunn, J., Fitzgibbons, S., & Pomorski, L.	Assess risk through environmental, social, and governance exposures.	Various companies	947	Empirical analysis
Navigating financial stability through the dual	D’Orazio, P.	Explore strategies for navigating financial stability	Financial institutions	947	Literature review

challenges of climate change and pandemics		amidst climate change and pandemics.			
The impact of corporate governance on the capital structure of companies from the energy industry	Grabinska, B., Kedzior, M., Kedzior, D., & Grabinski, K.	Investigate the impact of corporate governance on the capital structure of energy companies.	Energy industry firms	947	Empirical analysis